

GreenFORCE

Foster Research Excellence for Green Transition in the Western Balkans

D3.8 Report on the 2nd and 3rd Stand-alone Teaching Event

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List of project partners

Number	Role	Short name	Legal name	Country	PIC
1	COO	Co-PLAN	CO-PLAN INSTITUTI PER ZHVILLIMIN EHABIITATIT	AL	941177712
1.1	AE	U_POLIS	UNIVERSITETI POLIS SHPK	AL	954870232
2	BEN	POLITO	POLITECNICO DI TORINO	IT	999977754
3	BEN	NORDREGIO	NORDREGIO	SE	999536792
4	BEN	UB-GEF	UNIVERSITY OF BELGRADE - FACULTY OF GEOGRAPHY	RS	933015744
5	BEN	CEA	CENTER FOR ECONOMIC ANALYSES ASSOCIATION	MK	912445536

Executive Summary

D3.8 Report on the 2nd and 3rd Stand-alone Teaching Event details the activities conducted during the second and third Schools Activities in Belgrade (Serbia) in 2024 and Tirana (Albania) in 2025.

By the project's General Agreement, Greenforce organised three intensive international winter/summer schools, also known as stand-alone teaching events, to disseminate knowledge generated by the project itself.

Aligned with the project's central theme, "Just Green Transitions," the Belgrade Summer School focused on communicating just green transition as a powerful platform for communicating the importance of sustainability to the next generation. The outcomes were shared with numerous stakeholders and other representatives of the quadruple helix using different communication channels.

The Winter School in Tirana was an immersive platform for exploring how nature-based solutions (NBS) can scale down green transition efforts to the neighbourhood level. Organised by Co-PLAN and POLIS University with the contribution of Greenforce partners, the Winter School brought together students from across Europe and the Western Balkans to engage in lectures, fieldwork, and design studios focused on local environmental challenges. Participants translated complex sustainability concepts into tangible, context-sensitive proposals by combining theoretical inputs with hands-on urban explorations and collaborative scenario-building exercises.

These results were communicated to key stakeholders, including local government representatives, and further shared through project social media channels, reinforcing the role of education in advancing just, place-based green transitions.

This deliverable outlines the activities carried out by both schools and the contribution made by each partner. To facilitate understanding, the report is divided into two parts: Part 1 presents the Summer School experience in Belgrade, while Part 2 focuses on the Winter School held in Tirana. Each part has several sections presenting:

- The summer school organisation
- The summer school topic
- Main online and in-person activities
- Summer schools' main results

For each experience, a number of annexes are included.

1. Project Overview

GreenFORCE aims at fostering excellence in the "Western Balkans' green transition" scientific research and innovation of Co-PLAN, CEA, and UB-GEF as a means to enhancing their research profile, strengthening research and management capacities of their staff, and contributing to convergence between Western Balkans (WB) and EU research capacities, as well as to broader policy initiatives for the WB region. To achieve this objective, a twinning partnership of five organisations will work closely to produce territorial knowledge through exploratory research and institutional learning; transferring and exchanging knowledge among partner organisations through applying the knowledge management cycle, engaging in networking for sharing, cross-fertilizing and amplifying knowledge at the societal level. Ultimately, the ambition is to transcend from individual learning to enabling institutional learning, ensuring that scientific research and its management practices become institutionalised within the recipient organisations. GreenFORCE will contribute to the impacts of the destination "Improved access to excellence" by enabling pathways of cooperation, exchange, co-design, and co-creation with academia, civil society and policymakers at the regional level. The five partner organisations are Co-PLAN, Institute for

Habitat Development in Albania as the coordinating partner; University of Belgrade - Faculty of Geography (UB-GEF) in Serbia and the Center for Economic Analysis Association (CEA) in North Macedonia as the two regional partners; and Nordregio, a pan-Nordic research organisation based in Sweden, together with Politecnico di Torino, Italy (POLITO), as the leading EU research institutions. POLIS University in Albania is the affiliate partner of Co-PLAN.

3. Stand-alone Teaching Events in GreenFORCE

According to the Grant Agreement (page 24), all partners are engaged in organizing and implementing three stand-alone teaching events that contribute to the co-design/co-evaluation, exchange, and sharing of the research practice and results conducted in WP4. The events should be open to master's and Ph.D. students from U_POLIS, UB-GEF, and POLITO. Each event will host up to 20 students, of which 50% will be from the hosting institution. The guest institutions will bring five students and two researchers each. According to the project timetable, the stand-alone teaching events are organized as follows:

- September 2023, Turin, Italy
- May 2024, Belgrade, Serbia
- February 2025, Tirane, Albania

As agreed, the teaching staff is composed of researchers from the five partner institutions. Operationally, students are selected in advance through an open call, and the events enable researchers to produce and exchange knowledge on the just green transition. To communicate this activity, the project web site has a dedicated section - [Summer School – GreenFORCE \(greenforcetwinning.net\)](https://greenforcetwinning.net).

Part 1 – Summer School in Belgrade, Serbia

International Summer School

Communicating Just Green Transitions

Navigating the Path to a Sustainable Future

4 Summer School Organisation

The summer school in Belgrade was organised by the [University of Belgrade - Faculty of Geography \(UB-GEF\)](#) and is set in the framework of the Department for Spatial planning and supported by [Co-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development](#) in Albania as the coordinating partner; [Interuniversity Department of Urban and Regional Studies and Planning](#) and the [Interdepartmental Responsible Risk Resilience Centre \(R3C\)](#) of Politecnico di Torino in Italy the [Center for Economic Analysis Association \(CEA\)](#) in North Macedonia; and [Nordregio](#), a pan-Nordic research organisation based in Sweden. It aimed to involve students from different universities in identifying the challenges and opportunities of how to effectively communicate just and green transitions among diverse stakeholders. The students attended several lectures and working group activities that introduced the challenges they will have to focus on and present possible ways to approach them. Besides the local perspective, students learned from European and Western Balkans examples and case studies, being supervised and mentored by an international, multi-disciplinary teaching staff during their activity.

The summer school was organised in the following dates: 15 April 2024 (Day Zero - online kick-off meeting), 23 April 2024 (Day 1 -online lectures even), 24 April 2024 (Day 2 -online lectures even), 13-17 May 2024 (activities in Belgrade), 17 June 2024 (final presentations). The involved universities and institutions were: Co-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development (coordinating partner, AL); Polis University (AL); Politecnico di Torino – R3C Responsible Risk Resilience Centre (IT), Nordregio (SE), University of Belgrade – Faculty of Geography (RS) and Center for Economic Analyses Association (MK). The summer school involved 20 students from Politecnico di Torino, University of Belgrade and Polis University.

4.1 The Topic: “ Communicating Just Green Transitions - Navigating the Path to a Sustainable Future”

The imperative for a just green transition (JGT) has become increasingly evident in the face of global challenges such as climate change, resource depletion, and environmental degradation. As societies grapple with the need for sustainable development, effective communication plays a pivotal role in mobilizing public support, shaping policy decisions, and driving meaningful change. Thus is necessary to explore the multifaceted aspects of communicating the just green transition, examining key strategies, challenges, and the role of various stakeholders in fostering a collective commitment to a sustainable future. To effectively communicate the green transition, it is essential to move beyond traditional environmental narratives and frame the conversation in a way that resonates with diverse audiences. This involves emphasising the economic, social, and health benefits of sustainability. Communicators should underscore how green initiatives can create jobs, foster innovation, and improve public health, appealing to a broader spectrum of stakeholders, including businesses, policymakers, and the general public. Successful communication of the JGT requires collaboration among diverse stakeholders. Governments, businesses, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), and communities all play integral roles. Stakeholder engagement involves transparent communication, active listening, and the incorporation of diverse perspectives into sustainability initiatives. By fostering a sense of shared responsibility and inclusivity, a coalition for change can be built, promoting a more

effective and holistic approach to the JGT. Technology and innovation are instrumental in advancing the green transition. Communicating the potential of technological solutions, such as renewable energy, circular economies, and sustainable agriculture, is crucial in garnering support. Effectively communicating complex scientific concepts to the public enhances understanding and facilitates public buy-in. Moreover, highlighting success stories and showcasing tangible benefits of green technologies can inspire optimism and confidence in the transition process. Social networks play a pivotal role in boosting communication about the JGT, offering a powerful platform for disseminating information, fostering engagement, and building a community of environmentally conscious individuals. Leveraging social networks effectively can amplify the impact of sustainability initiatives and contribute to a broader understanding of the JGT. We can recognize numerous ways in which social networks can enhance communication efforts in promoting a JGT. A summer school program focuses on the communicating just green transition is a powerful platform for communicating the importance of sustainability to the next generation. With engaging curriculum, integrating interdisciplinary perspectives, leveraging technology, encouraging hands-on experiences, fostering collaboration, empowering advocacy, and showcasing success stories, students will be able to get a transformative learning experience. Through effective communication and hands-on engagement, summer school will play a pivotal role in shaping environmentally conscious and empowered young leaders who will contribute to a sustainable future.

4.2 Summer School Main Organisation Steps.

The organisation of the summer school in Belgrade followed three main steps (see Figure 1): (i) Step1 - co-design of the summer school topic with partners and preparation of the call lead by UB-GEF; Step 2 - launching of the call and students' selection (while UB_GEF coordinated the process while each partner followed internal rules depending on the each institutional organisation); Step 3 - the summer school implementation. Each step required specific actions/activities to implement and coordinate.

Figure 1 - 2nd Stand-alone Teaching Event in Belgrade: timetable and main steps

Summer School Topic Definition

As the task lead and host institution, UB-GEF took the initiative to compile a comprehensive list of potential topics aligned with the principles of just green transitions. This list was then shared with the project partners for collective consideration. To ensure the relevance and depth of these topics, the project team engaged in ad hoc meetings where each partner contributed to refining and providing additional details to the proposed subjects. The criteria guiding this collaborative refinement process were:

- *Consistency and Coherence with Just Green Transitions*: Ensuring that the selected topics align seamlessly with the overarching principles and objectives of just green transitions, fostering a cohesive and unified approach to the project's goals.
- *Relevance (Nationally and Internationally)*: Evaluating the significance of each topic on both national and international scales, taking into account the specific interests expressed by each partner. This approach helps in tailoring the content to meet the diverse needs and priorities of the participating institutions.
- *Capacity and Knowledge Sharing*: Assessing the collective capacity and knowledge held by the partners on each topic. This criterion ensures that the chosen subjects leverage the expertise and insights available within the consortium, fostering a collaborative environment for meaningful knowledge exchange.
- *Relevance for the Western Balkan's and replicability*): Considering the impact and applicability of the selected topics within the local context, particularly focusing on the interests of WB's and other key stakeholders. This criterion helps in aligning the project outcomes with the specific needs and challenges of the project's immediate surroundings.

Through a collaborative and iterative process, these criteria have guided the selection and detailing of topics, ensuring that the stand-alone teaching events are academically robust and closely tailored to the unique context and goals of the project.

Call Preparation

UB-GEF has coordinated the preparation of the call in conjunction with all partners involved. As Annex 1a shows, a document was prepared including some info regarding among the others:

- The focus and main activities;
- The context - Navigating the Path to a Sustainable Future;
- Eligibility Requirements, language, ECTS credits;
- Selection Criteria and Ethics.

The Launch of the Summer School

The call has been launched simultaneously by each partner and communicated by the project website at the following link - [Communicating Just Green Transitions Navigating the Path to a Sustainable](#)

Future - Communicating Just Green Transitions – Navigating the Path to a Sustainable Future – GreenFORCE.

Student Selection

Each institution has selected students according to the following criteria (see annex 2a – list of students):

The students have been selected on the basis of the following criteria:

- interest-driving learning in the contents of the summer school students are applying to (i.e., operationalising just and green transition) based on the motivation letter;
- background and preparation based on the CV and/or the portfolio;
- research skills and attitudes based on the CV and/or the portfolio;

An evaluation committee composed of institutional staff involved in the teaching activity assessed the candidates. The list of selected candidates ensured a balanced representation of gender. No discrimination has been based on nationality, sexual orientation, or political opinion. Each institution guaranteed to maintain a selection process that is fair and equitable, and support informed and responsible decision-making of candidates.

The summer school activity is explained in the following section.

5. Summer school main activity conducted

5.1 Online Kick-off

The online kick-off meeting of the international Summer School “Communicating Just Green Transitions - Navigating the Path to a Sustainable Future” was held on the 16th of April 2024. The event involved the 20 international students from U_Polis (Albania), UB-GEF (Serbia) and Polito. The teaching staff also involved international researchers from the 6 partner institutions: CEA (North Macedonia), Co-PLAN (Albania), Nordregio (Sweden), UB-GEF, U_Polis and Singidunum University - The Faculty of Media and Communications (Serbia). The general topics of Just Green Transition and communications were introduced in the context of global challenges such as climate change, resource depletion, and environmental degradation. The online meeting was organized with an opening and welcoming, then a presentation of the GreenFORCE project was proposed to the students. An introduction to the summer school topic, methodology, agenda and main activities was shared and partners’ and students’ had the opportunity to present themselves. A first introduction to the topic of Just Green Transitions has been delivered by Carlos Tapia (Nordregio). A second introduction to the topic of What About Communication? has been delivered by Vojislav Zanetic (FMK).

On April 23rd first day of online lectures was held. Elena Gotovska from CEA presented the topic Towards Just Transition: Navigating Change through Effective Governance and Communication, while lecture Territorial Resilience and JGT was given by the Grazia Brunetta and Ombretta Caldarice from POLITO. Next day, on April 24th students received two more important lecturers: Climate literacy and science communication for emergencies - exploring tools, datasets and processes by Kejt Dražmi from Co-PLAN and JGT- Towards urban mobility strategy in Kragujevac, Republic of Serbia by Marija Jević from UB-GEF.

5.2 In-Presence Summer School in Belgrade

UB-GEF hosted the in-person activities of the Summer School from the 13th to the 17th of May 2024. The general topic of Communicating Just Green Transitions.

Day 1- Setting the context

On the first day, after an opening and welcoming with Velimir Šećerov, Dean of the UB-GEF and Aleksandar Đorđević, Greenforce UB-GEF Team Coordinator, a synthetic introduction of the summer school was provided by Aleksandar Đorđević and Branko Protić. Then,

Lecture: LOST IN COMMUNICATION (The importance of public communication for science — Introduction)

Speaker: Vojislav Žanetić

Time: 11:00 – 11:45

This introductory lecture sets the stage for the workshop by exploring the fundamental role of public communication in science. Vojislav Žanetić, a seasoned media and public discourse expert, will guide participants through the complexities and challenges researchers face when attempting to communicate scientific knowledge to a broader, often non-specialist, audience.

The session addressed questions such as:

- Why does science often get "lost in communication"?
- What are the key barriers to effective scientific communication?

- How can scientists better engage with the public without compromising rigor?

Žanetić linked theory with real-world examples to illustrate how strategic communication practices can elevate the social impact of science, counter misinformation, and strengthen the trust between scientific institutions and society. This session serves as a thought-provoking entry point into the broader theme of science and communication in contemporary media ecologies.

Lecture: SOCIAL NETWORKING (The role, significance, and means of content communication on social networks in the hyperconnected Society of the Spectacle)

Speakers: *Simona Žikić, PhD and/or Pavle Trifunović*

Time: 11:45 – 12:00

This dynamic short lecture focuses on social networks as communication ecosystems, examining how content is created, shared, and consumed in today's hyperconnected world — often described through Guy Debord's concept of the "Society of the Spectacle."

Simona Žikić (and/or Pavle Trifunović) discussed:

- The transformation of communication logics in the digital age.
- How attention, virality, and performance shape the visibility of content.
- Strategies for scientists and communicators to use platforms like Twitter/X, Instagram, TikTok, and LinkedIn effectively — not just to broadcast messages, but to foster dialogue and engagement.

This lecture bridges theoretical insights and practical considerations, emphasising the significance of platform-specific content design and the emotional economy of digital communication.

Subdivision into groups, meeting with the tutors and organisation of the work

Time: 12:00 – 13:00

Following the morning lectures, participants were divided into working groups. To each group was assigned a communication tutor — a specialist in media, public relations, or science communication — who will facilitate and mentor their work throughout the practical session.

Topic discussed:

- Establish the group dynamics and clarify roles.
- Discuss expectations, timelines, and deliverables.
- Begin brainstorming topics or themes for the afternoon practice session.

The emphasis is on collaborative learning, with tutors acting as both guides and catalysts, helping groups transform conceptual knowledge into communicative strategies.

Practice: JUST DOING IT — Work in the classroom under communication tutors' supervision

Time: 13:00 – 16:00

This hands-on session is the core of the day's activities. Under the theme "Just Doing It," participants applied the lessons from the morning by creating communication outputs aimed at translating complex scientific ideas into accessible content for a broader audience.

Working in their assigned groups, participants may choose from a range of formats, including:

- A short video or social media campaign
- An infographic or visual explainer
- A simulated press release or interview script
- A podcast snippet or story pitch for a general-interest outlet

Tutors will provide continuous feedback, helping refine messages, sharpen narratives, and adapt the tone and format for the intended audience. The exercise encourages creativity, experimentation, and interdisciplinary collaboration, culminating in outputs that may be presented or shared at a later stage of the program.

Day 2 – Exploring the potential of communication tools

9.00 – 9.45: Lecture – *POSTED TO BE SPOTTED*

Speaker: Fahri Dashwalli

The day begins with an insightful lecture on the strategic use of social media as a tool for public communication, personal branding, and the dissemination of relevant content in both professional and institutional contexts. Fahri Dashwalli will guide participants through a critical exploration of the most widely used platforms—Instagram, X (formerly Twitter), Facebook, and emerging social networks—highlighting their core features, differences in content formats, audience engagement strategies, and best practices for gaining visibility and impact. The lecture will also address key aspects such as algorithms, engagement metrics, reputational risks, and digital ethics. Special emphasis will be placed on building a coherent narrative across posts, developing an editorial plan, and tailoring content to the unique language and culture of each platform.

10.00 – 10.45: Lecture – VENI, VINI, VIDEO**Speaker: Tijana Dedić**

In this session, Tijana Dedić introduces the essentials of video production for social media, with a focus on platforms such as YouTube, Instagram, and TikTok. The aim is to equip students with the foundational skills needed to conceptualise, shoot, edit, and publish short-form video content that is visually engaging and effectively communicates key messages. The lecture will cover basic technical aspects—including framing, lighting, and sound—as well as creative elements such as storytelling, editing techniques, and the use of trending formats. Attention will also be given to platform-specific algorithms and how to optimize videos for reach and viewer retention.

11.00 – 11.45: Lecture – FROM CAST TO CAST**Speaker: Luka Bešliagić, PhD**

This session focuses on the fast-growing world of podcasts and minicasts. Luka Bešliagić, PhD, will walk students through the core components of audio content creation, from concept development and scripting to recording, editing, and publishing. The lecture will explore different podcast formats (interviews, solo episodes, panel discussions), distribution platforms, and audience engagement strategies. Participants will also learn about the equipment and software needed to produce quality audio content, as well as the importance of voice, tone, and pacing. Emphasis will be placed on how to use podcasts as an effective communication tool for knowledge sharing, advocacy, and storytelling.

13.00 – 16.00: Practice – WORK MORE, DO MORE**Supervised practical session with communication tutors**

In the afternoon, participants will apply the knowledge acquired during the morning lectures through a hands-on practice session, working directly under the supervision of communication tutors. Students will be divided into small groups and tasked with producing content in one or more of the formats discussed—social media posts, short videos, or podcast/minicast segments. This session is designed to foster teamwork, creativity, and critical thinking while offering practical experience in content creation and digital communication strategies. Tutors will provide feedback and guidance throughout the process, helping students refine their outputs and prepare for real-world communication challenges.

Day 3 – Meeting with International Organisation,

Student's visit to the UNDP

The third day of the programme featured a highly engaging and instructive visit by the students to the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) office, offering them a valuable opportunity to gain real-world insights into sustainable development practices. This visit aimed to bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and applied practice by exposing students to the concrete activities and strategic priorities of a major international development organization operating in the region. During the visit, students were welcomed by UNDP staff and participated in an interactive session that

introduced the organization's mission, core areas of intervention, and its specific role in supporting Serbia's efforts towards a more inclusive and sustainable development trajectory. The session covered a wide range of pressing regional issues, with particular emphasis on the challenges and opportunities related to climate change, territorial development, and the just green transition. These themes were not only discussed in abstract terms but were illustrated through specific project examples and policy initiatives currently being implemented by UNDP in Serbia. In an open and stimulating atmosphere that encouraged dialogue and exchange, students had the opportunity to pose questions, reflect critically on the role of international organizations, and discuss how sustainability objectives are translated into concrete actions on the ground. They learned how the UNDP functions as a key regional actor, promoting innovation, fostering local partnerships, and supporting the alignment of national policies with broader global frameworks such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The experience was further enriched by a creative workshop held after the visit, which focused on practical design and problem-solving exercises under the supervision of the JGT tutors. This hands-on component allowed students to process the information received during the visit and apply their insights to develop ideas and proposals related to sustainable urban and territorial development. The workshop fostered teamwork, creativity, and critical thinking, providing a dynamic setting in which students could explore how theoretical concepts and institutional strategies intersect with local realities and tangible outcomes. More importantly, the day helped students to internalize the relevance and urgency of sustainability-related issues in both policy and practice. By engaging directly with professionals and being exposed to real-world challenges and initiatives, students came away with a stronger understanding of how multi-level governance, climate policies, and development strategies are interconnected—and why their role as future planners, policymakers, and change agents is more crucial than ever.

13.00 - 16.00: Practice and Creation - DO-IT-YOURSELF

During this hands-on session, students will actively engage in the practical application of communication techniques and tools. Working in small groups under the supervision of JGT tutors, participants will:

- Develop their own communication outputs (e.g., press releases, short videos, social media posts, infographics, or podcasts) based on a given brief or topic.
- Experiment with storytelling methods and formats tailored to different audiences and media channels.
- Practice using digital tools for editing, design, and publishing.
- Receive real-time feedback from tutors to refine their content and delivery.
- Collaborate with peers to simulate a real-world communication team environment.

Day 4 – Make the difference: communicate, communicate, communicate

3.00 – 16.00: City Tour – Discovering Communication in Context

This guided city tour offers students the opportunity to explore Turin through a communication lens. Accompanied by JGT tutors, students will observe and reflect on how the city tells its story through urban signs, public spaces, cultural landmarks, and media. The tour will highlight examples of strategic communication in urban branding, heritage promotion, and civic engagement. Students will be encouraged to take notes, photos, and short videos to use as inspiration or material for their group projects.

Day 5 – Practice and Creation: DO-IT-YOURSELF – Final Sprint

Under the continued supervision of JGT tutors, students will return to their classroom workspace to finalize and polish their group outputs. This session is dedicated to implementing the last revisions based on feedback, improving visuals and narratives, and preparing for presentation.

13.00 – 15.45: Intermediate Presentations, Discussion, and Wrap-Up

In the final segment of the course, each of the five student groups will present their work-in-progress communication strategies for the city of Turin. This is a key moment for peer learning and feedback. Presentations will be followed by a roundtable discussion involving professors, tutors, and fellow participants, offering constructive critiques, suggestions for improvement, and broader reflections on the communication approaches adopted. The session concludes with a collective wrap-up to synthesize insights, share experiences, and celebrate the achievements of the group.

5.3 Online Final presentations

The final activities of the Summer School were conducted online on the 17th of June 2024, concluding an intensive and multidisciplinary learning experience. During this final session, the students had the opportunity to present the outcomes of their group work, which had been developed over the course of the program through collaborative and cross-sectoral approaches. These final products included analytical reports, spatial scenarios, policy recommendations, and communication tools, depending on the specific focus of each working group. The presentations were followed by a structured discussion involving the professors, tutors, and mentors who had accompanied the participants throughout the Summer School. This moment of collective reflection allowed for an in-depth exchange of perspectives on the methodologies adopted, the relevance and feasibility of the proposed solutions, and the broader implications for policy and practice. The feedback provided by the academic and professional experts aimed not only to evaluate the quality of the outputs but also to encourage critical thinking and future development. The materials produced by the students, including presentations, written reports, and visual outputs, were collected, reviewed, and commented on by the teaching staff. A final compilation of the materials was prepared and delivered in a shared digital repository, with the aim of making them accessible to the wider community of stakeholders involved in the thematic areas addressed by the Summer School. These stakeholders included public authorities, planning agencies, civil society organisations, and other relevant actors who may benefit from the insights and proposals elaborated during the program. This final phase of dissemination reflects the Summer School's commitment to knowledge transfer and to fostering a dialogue between academia and society.

6. Summer school main results and outputs

The activity conducted allowed the students to work in a multidisciplinary and international environment. The 20 students have been organised in 5 teams, each constituted by 4 students (2 from UB-GEF, 1 from POLITO and 1 from U_Polis).

Task 1 for each group was creating one post for Facebook and Instagram regarding our seminar, including photo/video content and text, at least one Instagram story (preferably more), and recording material for an Instagram reel, TikTok and/or YouTube shorts. The second task was to create content for social media related to the Green transition. They applied what they have learned in the lectures held before this workshop. Each group needed to create one post for Facebook and Instagram, including photo/video content and text, at least one Instagram story (preferably more), and record material for an Instagram reel, TikTok and/or YouTube shorts. The last task was dedicated to creating a sort of mini-podcast (minicast). One member of the group acted as the host and interview another, while the third will record. They discussed the seminar and the topic of the Green transition.

Here we offer a brief contextualisation of the topics addressed by each team.

Team 1 - Green Cat

Meet the Green Cat, our symbol of a just green transition! 🌿🐱 Ever wondered about pollution and climate change in the Western Balkans, and what you can do to improve it? You're in the right place! Every person is affected by pollution and climate change, and contributes to it. Let's learn together and make changes in our environment!

The Green Agenda for the Western Balkans aligns with the European Green Deal, aiming for carbon neutrality (i.e. no emissions of CO₂) by 2050 to combat climate change and address regional environmental challenges. This includes promoting renewable energy, improving air and water quality, and conserving biodiversity. 🌍 I'll show you simple steps to incorporate into your daily life for a greener, eco-responsible lifestyle. The future isn't something we wait for - it's something we create. 🌱
#GreenTransition #Sustainability #CleanEnergy #ProtectOurPlanet

🌿 Discover the 5 Pillars of the Green Agenda for the Western Balkans:

1. Clean Energy & Climate Protection: Transition to renewables and reduce emissions.
2. Circular Economy: Promote recycling, waste management, and sustainable production.
3. Pollution Reduction:

Improve air, water, and soil quality. 4. Sustainable Agriculture: Enhance food security and eco-friendly farming. 5. Biodiversity Protection: Safeguard natural habitats and ecosystems.

Join us in creating a greener, healthier future! 🌍🌱 #GreenAgenda #Sustainability #CleanEnergy #CircularEconomy #PollutionReduction #SustainableAgriculture #Biodiversity

5 pillars of Green Agenda for WESTERN BALKANS

1 Cleaning energy sources, protecting the climate

The Western Balkans faces significant climate challenges due to its coal dependency, necessitating a transition to cleaner, renewable energy sources to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and enhance climate resilience.

2 Moving to a circular economy

Transitioning to a circular economy is vital for the Western Balkans to achieve sustainability objectives, emphasizing enhancements in raw material, production sustainability, waste management strategies, and the mitigation of plastic pollution, especially in water bodies.

4 Building sustainable agriculture and food systems

Agriculture contributes around 10% to the Western Balkans' GDP, highlighting the urgency to enhance rural development, improve food security and quality, reduce waste, ensure compliance with safety and animal welfare standards, and promote eco-friendly farming practices.

3 Depolluting air, water and soil

Pollution is a major challenge in the Western Balkans, underscoring the pillar's aim to align with EU standards for air quality, water, and wastewater. This includes upgrading monitoring systems, investing more in wastewater management, and encouraging water reuse in agriculture.

5 Protecting biodiversity and ecosystems

The Western Balkans boast rich habitats and biodiversity, requiring protection for future generations and establishment of Western Balkans 2030 Biodiversity Action Plan and a Forest Landscape Restoration Plan, supported by EU.

Did you know that Tirana and Belgrade often have air pollution levels exceeding WHO guidelines? 😞 Sadly, over 30,000 people in the Western Balkans pass away prematurely every year due to poor air quality. Traffic is a major contributor to this problem, especially in cities. 🚗➡️🚶🚲🚊 Opting for alternatives like walking 🚶 biking 🚲 or public transport 🚊 can help reduce harmful emissions. These actions support the pillars 01 - Cleaning energy sources, protecting the climate, and 03 - Depolluting air, water and soil, of Green Agenda for the Western Balkans 🌍🌱 #AirQuality #CleanEnergy #GreenAgenda #WalkBikeRide

Water pollution is a big problem in Western Balkans, harming rivers, lakes, and coastal areas. Industrial activities, poor wastewater treatment, runoff from farms, and illegal waste dumping are major contributors. While some efforts have been made to tackle these issues, many challenges persist. In Serbia, a large percentage (around 85%) of sewage goes directly into rivers, far exceeding EU standards. Currently, 70% of communities lack proper wastewater treatment, but new treatment plants are being built. Similarly, in Albania, there is a shortage of wastewater treatment plants, especially in rural areas and smaller communities, while existing wastewater treatment infrastructure is often outdated and in need of repair or modernization.

To join the fight against water pollution you can reduce water usage, waste disposal responsibly, and advocate for change in your community to protect our precious water resources 🌿 Every drop counts! In this way we will contribute to pillars 03 - Depolluting air, water and soil, and 05 - Protecting biodiversity and ecosystems, of Green Agenda for the Western Balkans 🌍🌿 #WaterPollution #CleanWater #ProtectOurPlanet #GreenAgenda #EveryDropCounts

Discover the contrasting energy landscape of Serbia and Albania! Serbia's heavy reliance on coal leads to significant greenhouse gas emissions and air pollution, exacerbated by outdated infrastructure and inefficient energy production. Meanwhile, Albania taps into hydropower, a renewable source, but grapples with ecosystem changes due to dam construction. It's clear that transitioning to renewables isn't without impact: even renewable sources like hydropower can alter and harm ecosystems. However, with careful planning and management of our energy resources, we can mitigate negative effects and pave the way towards a more sustainable future.

To drive positive change, let's focus on what we as individuals can do:

- 💡 **Conserve Energy:** Turn off lights & electronics when not in use, use energy-efficient appliances, and insulate your home for better energy efficiency.
- ⚙️ **Promote Renewable Energy:** Consider installing solar panels or supporting renewable energy sources to reduce reliance on fossil fuels.
- 🗣️ **Advocate for Sustainability:** Stay informed about environmental policies and advocate for initiatives that prioritize renewable energy and environmental protection.

In this way we can contribute to the pillars 01 - Cleaning energy sources, protecting the climate, and 05 - Protecting biodiversity and ecosystems, of Green Agenda for the Western Balkans #EnergyTransition #RenewableEnergy #Sustainability #CleanEnergy #GreenFuture

Team 2 - Green bubble

Green washing vs the green transition

Green Transition: This concept involves genuine efforts to shift towards more sustainable and environmentally friendly practices. It encompasses a wide range of initiatives aimed at reducing carbon emissions, promoting renewable energy sources, improving resource efficiency, and protecting biodiversity. In the Balkans, the green transition may involve policies and investments in renewable energy infrastructure, waste management systems, sustainable agriculture practices, and initiatives to protect and restore natural habitats. It's about making fundamental changes to the way societies and economies operate to ensure long-term environmental sustainability.

Green agenda for the western balkans

me when I find out about the agenda

THE AGENDA AIMS TO HELP THE REGION **COMBAT CLIMATE CHANGE** AND IMPROVE RELATIONS WITH THE EU

BASED ON **5 PILLARS**:
DECARBONIZATION, CIRCULAR ECONOMY, DEPOLLUTION, BIODIVERSITY AND SUSTAINABLE FOOD SYSTEMS.

a big step for the just green transitions

or is it?

THE GREEN TRANSITIONS TO BE JUST MUST ALSO BRING **SOCIAL EQUITY**

“Linking health, social, and climate justice can lead to the transformative activism that is needed for a better, healthier, and fairer world for everyone.”
Rouf K. Wainwright T.

THE AGENDA DOES **NOT** EXPLICITLY MENTION THE PROBLEM.

HOWEVER IT WANTS TO **ENCOURAGE TRANSPARENCY AND PUBLIC PARTICIPATION** BY HELPING LOCAL GOVERNMENTS.

but it may not be enough

Should the Green Agenda be more incisive?

what do you think
leave a comment

GREEN BUBBLE

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Greenwashing: This term refers to the practice of conveying a false impression or providing misleading information about how a company's products are more environmentally sound. It often involves companies engaging in superficial or insincere efforts to appear environmentally friendly without making substantial changes to their practices. In the Balkans, as elsewhere, greenwashing can manifest in various forms, such as cosmetic changes to packaging, misleading advertising claims, or token sustainability initiatives that don't address the core environmental impacts of a business or industry.

 Green FORCE

IS AN **URBAN RENEWAL DEVELOPMENT PROJECT** AIMED AT IMPROVING BELGRADE'S CITYSCAPE AND ECONOMY BY REVITALIZING A NEGLECTED STRETCH OF LAND ON THE **RIGHT BANK OF THE SAVA RIVER**.

THE PROJECT WAS INITIATED IN 2014 BETWEEN THE GOVERNMENT OF SERBIA AND ABU DHABI-BASED PRIVATE INVESTMENT COMPANY.

@green_bubble_

ON THE OFFICIAL **WEBSITE** THE PROJECT IS PRESENTED LIKE THIS

“ The life you’ve been dreaming about is right in front of you. A state-of-the-art bilingual elementary school with a kindergarten, museums, parks with plenty of greenery, sports fields... ”

@green_bubble_

 Green FORCE

This school may not be for you and your family

UNLESS YOU LIVE IN ONE OF THE **EXPENSIVE NEW APARTMENTS**, YOU WON'T BE ABLE TO USE THE SCHOOL.

@green_bubble_

 Green FORCE

Do you know other cases of greenwashing?

tell us about it in the comments

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Team 3 – SandBox

The name "Sandbox" for a workshop on Green Transition suggests a space for experimentation, creativity and innovation. Just like children play and experiment in a sandbox, participants in this workshop would have the freedom to explore new ideas, technologies and approaches to foster environmental sustainability. It represents a collaborative and dynamic environment where ideas can be tested, refined and implemented to drive the transition towards a greener future.

Slogan: Let's shape a greener future!

Theme: Tailoring the Green Transition (according to us and our needs)

Tailoring in the context of Green Transition refers to CUSTOMIZING or ADAPTING strategies, policies, and actions which the EU imposes on Western Balkan countries, to suit their specific contexts, needs and challenges related to sustainability and environmental conservation. Tailoring involves taking into account factors such as geographic location, socio-economic conditions, cultural norms and technological capabilities to develop effective and contextually relevant solutions for promoting green initiatives.

Since human societies have created the path that has led to the current climate and environmental crisis, it stands to reason that radical change would involve an equally profound change in the societies themselves. So what Western Balkan countries can do to mitigate this changes or at last adapt to them?

The main goal is to explore how and how much Western Balkan countries can adapt to the Just Green Transition and Green Agenda taking it as a base and tailoring the policies, strategies, that suits them best to promote socially Just Transition among all the stakeholders involved

Our topic is the possibility of adaptation or, better said, the tailoring of the Green Transition. Tailoring the Green Transition involves ensuring that climate action is fair, inclusive, and considers the well-being of people and the planet.

Tailoring the European Green Deal for Serbia and Albania
Addressing Unique Challenges and Opportunities

Economic Constraints in Serbia and Albania

GDP per Capita Disparities

Country	GDP per Capita (\$)
Serbia	8.7k
Albania	5.3k
Germany	45.7k

Existing Fiscal and Public Debts

Debt Impact

Debt to GDP ratio (%)

Country	Debt to GDP ratio (%)
Serbia	56.5%
Albania	74.5%

Social Challenges in Serbia and Albania

Comparing Unemployment Rates and Poverty Risks

Category	Serbia	Albania
Unemployment Rates	11.1%	11.5%
Poverty Risks	23.4%	23.0%

Environmental Challenges

Impacts of Air Pollution and Recycling Rates in Belgrade and Tirana

Belgrade and Tirana face significant challenges with elevated air pollution levels, impacting the environment and public health.

Serbia's 22% recycling rate and Albania's underdeveloped recycling infrastructure, highlight the need for substantial improvements to align with the EU average of 48%.

Governance and Implementation Issues

Addressing Corruption Challenges in Serbia and Albania

Serbia: 96th in Corruption Index
Serbia ranks 96th in the Corruption Perceptions Index 2022, indicating governance challenges.

Albania: 110th in Corruption Index
Albania ranks 110th in the Corruption Perceptions Index 2022, highlighting governance issues.

Policy Execution Hicrance
Governance challenges in both countries hinder effective policy implementation and execution.

Energy Dependence and Poverty

Understanding Energy Sources and Poverty Challenges

Serbia's Energy Mix
Serbia heavily relies on coal for over 70% of its energy needs.

Albania's Energy Sources
Albania has a significant dependence (100%) on hydropower to meet its energy demands.

EU Comparison
In comparison to the EU average, where 8.2% experience energy poverty, both Serbia and Albania encounter higher levels of energy poverty.

Energy Poverty Concerns
A substantial portion of the population in both countries faces challenges in accessing sufficient.

EU Accession and Green Deal Alignment

Advancing EU Candidacy and Aligning Green Deal Objectives

START → END

EU Candidacy Progress: Serbia and Albania moving forward in EU accession procedures.

Implementation Support: Enhancing policy execution through EU alignment.

Policy Integration: Harmonizing Green Deal initiatives with EU accession requirements.

Sustainable Transition: Balancing EU aspirations with environmental sustainability.

A Tailored Approach for Effective Implementation

Addressing Unique Contexts of Serbia and Albania

Economic Context
SRB: Invest in greener energy and offer business incentives for eco-friendly practices.
ALB: Develop export-oriented organic agriculture.

Social Context
Implement vocational training programs focused on green jobs in both countries to reduce unemployment and poverty risk.

Environmental Context
Both countries could implement urban greenery projects to combat air pollution, such as planting trees and creating parks.

Governance Context
Enhance transparency and accountability mechanisms in environmental governance to improve rankings on the CPI.

Energy Context
SRB: Expand into renewables like wind and solar.
ALB: Complement hydropower with solar and wind energy.

EU Integration
Leverage EU candidacy status to access funds and technical expertise for green projects.

Team 4 – EcoEcho

🌍💡 Meet EcoEcho, the vibrant team of students from the University of Belgrade, Torino, and Tirana, united under the Green Force project's summer school. Our mission? To amplify the message of a just green transition. 🗣️🔊 Our name is a blend of 'ECO' –symbolizing our commitment to ecology–and 'ECHO', representing our drive to ensure our green message resonates far and wide. With a logo bathed in light pastel blue for clarity and calm, and dark blue for depth and stability, we're here to make sustainability heard! ❤️🗨️ #EcoEcho #GreenForce #JustGreenTransition #SustainabilityInAction

🌱 Ever heard of the ‘Green Transition’? It’s our pathway to a brighter, more sustainable future! 🌟 But what does it involve? Imagine a world where our climate, energy, and mobility systems are in harmony with nature. 🌾☀️🚲 Where our food systems nourish both people and the planet. 🌊🌿 Where pollution is a problem of the past. ♻️🔄 Where we reuse and recycle, creating a circular economy that wastes nothing. ♻️🔄 And where every form of life thrives, enriching our biodiversity. 🐝🌳 These are the five pillars that uphold our shift to green development. Let’s build this future together! 🤝🌍 #GreenTransition #SustainableFuture #ClimateAction #CircularEconomy #Biodiversity

🚶🌳 Mobility is the heartbeat of urban development and a key driver in the green transition. It’s about connecting people with places in a way that’s sustainable for both the environment and our communities. 🏠🚶 Public transportation reduces our carbon footprint, while mixed-use development blends living, working, and leisure spaces for a vibrant, accessible city life. 🏡🌳 Green spaces offer a breath of fresh air, promoting health and well-being. Together, they create cities that are not just livable, but lovable - for us and the planet. 🌍🤝 #UrbanMobility #GreenTransition #SustainableCities #PublicTransport #GreenSpaces

A tale of two cities within one frame: On the left, a bustling street clogged with cars symbolizing conventional urban mobility. On the right, a serene urban park with pedestrians, cyclists, and abundant greenery representing sustainable mobility. A clear divide runs down the center, contrasting the two sides. Which side do you prefer? Swipe left for the full picture and share your thoughts below! 🌳 🏙️
 #CityLife #UrbanMobility #SustainableLiving

🚶‍♀️🏙️ AI and the Future of Walkable Cities 🏙️🚶‍♂️ Imagine a city where walking is not just a mode of transport, but a delightful, efficient, and safe experience. AI is transforming urban walkability, making our streets smarter, greener, and more inclusive for everyone. 🚶‍♂️🌳 From smart crosswalks and adaptive traffic lights to real-time information displays and sidewalk sensors, AI is enhancing the pedestrian experience. Walkability means cleaner air, healthier lifestyles, and vibrant communities. Let's step into the future, one AI-powered stride at a time! 🚶‍♂️🌱

Navigating Belgrade's Transit Turmoil 🚶‍♂️🇧🇪🚆 - Our deep dive into the city's 'revolutionary' transport plans reveals a paradox: despite ambitious designs for trains, metros, and trams, car usage is set to rise 📈. Why? We unpack the masterplan's mixed signals and what it means for walkers and riders alike. #BelgradeTransport #UrbanPlanning #Walkability #PublicTransit

Belgrade oftentimes has optimistic plans for its future development. Therefore they are planning a basic revolution in terms of walkability, particularly public transportation.

But... Where is it in data?

Car ownership per 1000 residents forecast (Belgrade masterplan)

Share of transportation types forecast (Belgrade masterplan)

Plan for Belgrade's railway, metro and tram system

Team 5 – Ultra Green

1. What is the green transition?

The green transition is the process of moving towards a society that is sustainable, with less negative impact on the environment. This includes reducing greenhouse gas emissions, using renewable energy sources, using resources more efficiently and promoting sustainable practices in industry, transport and everyday life.

2. Why is the green transition the best way to sustain the development of the planet?

The green transition is crucial for maintaining the development of the planet for several reasons, the most significant of which are the reduction of harmful gas emissions, the transition to cleaner sources of energy and technology that helps reduce global warming and climate change.

The transition is also significant because of a healthier environment, reducing air, water and land pollution improves people's quality of life and contributes to a healthier planet.

The green transition also promotes sustainable development that balances the needs of current and future generations without endangering ecosystems and natural resources.

The green transition refers to the shift from a traditional, fossil fuel-based economy to one that is more sustainable and environmentally friendly. This transition involves adopting renewable energy sources, improving energy efficiency, reducing carbon emissions, and promoting sustainable practices in various sectors such as transportation, construction, and agriculture. The goal is to mitigate climate change, protect natural resources, and create a more sustainable future.

🌿 Green Agenda for the Western Balkans 🌿

Did you know that the Western Balkans are on a path to a sustainable future? The Green Agenda, adopted in 2020, aligns with the European Green Deal and focuses on transforming our region into a green, low-carbon economy. Here's how:

🔌 **Renewable Energy:** Investing in solar, wind, and hydro power to reduce reliance on fossil fuels and lower emissions.

🏠 **Energy Efficiency:** Implementing measures to save energy in buildings, industries, and transport.

🌍 **Climate Action:** Committing to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and adapt to climate change impacts.

♻️ **Circular Economy:** Promoting recycling, reducing waste, and reusing materials to create a sustainable economy.

🌿 **Biodiversity:** Protecting our natural landscapes and wildlife, ensuring a rich and diverse environment.

🚫 **Fighting Pollution:** Tackling air, water, and soil pollution to create healthier communities.

This comprehensive agenda aims to ensure that the transition to a greener economy benefits everyone, leaving no one behind. Together, we can build a sustainable and inclusive future! 🌿🌿

#GreenAgenda #WesternBalkans #SustainableFuture #RenewableEnergy #EnergyEfficiency
#ClimateAction #CircularEconomy #Biodiversity #FightPollution #EcoFriendly

The green transition refers to the shift from a traditional, fossil fuel-based economy to one that is more sustainable and environmentally friendly. This transition involves adopting renewable energy sources, improving energy efficiency, reducing carbon emissions, and promoting sustainable practices in various sectors such as transportation, construction, and agriculture. The goal is to mitigate climate change, protect natural resources, and create a more sustainable future.

Green Transition in Turin, Italy

Turin, a city in northern Italy, has been proactive in pursuing a green transition through various initiatives aimed at sustainability and reducing its carbon footprint. Here are some key actions and results from Turin's efforts:

1. Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency:

Solar Energy: Turin has been investing in solar energy projects, installing photovoltaic panels on public buildings and promoting the use of solar power in residential areas.

Energy Efficiency Programs: The city has implemented energy efficiency programs for buildings, including retrofitting public buildings to reduce energy consumption and encouraging private building owners to adopt energy-efficient technologies.

2. Sustainable Mobility:

Public Transportation: Turin has enhanced its public transportation system, focusing on making it more efficient and environmentally friendly. This includes expanding the metro system and modernizing buses and trams to use cleaner energy.

Biking and Walking: The city has promoted cycling and walking by developing extensive bike lanes and pedestrian zones. This not only reduces traffic congestion but also lowers emissions from vehicles.

3. Green Spaces and Urban Planning:

Urban Green Spaces: Turin has increased its green spaces, including parks and gardens, to improve air quality and provide recreational areas for residents. Projects like the regeneration of the Dora River Park have transformed industrial areas into green, accessible public spaces.

Sustainable Urban Development: The city has integrated sustainability into its urban planning processes, ensuring that new developments are environmentally friendly and resource-efficient.

4. Waste Management and Circular Economy:

Recycling Programs: Turin has implemented comprehensive recycling programs to reduce waste and promote the circular economy. The city has set up recycling centers and campaigns to encourage residents to recycle more effectively.

Waste-to-Energy: Some of the city's waste is converted into energy through waste-to-energy plants, reducing landfill use and generating electricity from non-recyclable waste.

Results and Achievements

Turin has seen several positive outcomes from its green transition initiatives:

Reduced Emissions: Through various measures, Turin has managed to reduce its carbon emissions, contributing to Italy's overall climate goals.

Increased Renewable Energy Use: The city's investments in renewable energy have led to a significant increase in the use of solar power and other renewable sources.

Improved Air Quality: Initiatives to promote public transportation, cycling, and walking, along with the creation of green spaces, have resulted in better air quality in the city.

Enhanced Public Awareness: Public awareness about sustainability and the importance of the green transition has increased, leading to greater community involvement in environmental initiatives.

Overall, Turin's commitment to the green transition is evident in its comprehensive approach to sustainability, involving energy, transportation, urban planning, and waste management. The city continues to work towards its goals, setting an example for other cities aiming to achieve a greener, more sustainable future.

Air pollution in ALBANIA

Since April 2018, Milieukontakt Albania and Co-Plan have been monitoring air quality in Tirana through the Green Lungs project, funded by the European Union.

In the 2019 Pollution Index by Numbeo, Tirana is listed as one of the most polluted cities in Europe, based on citizens' perceptions. The city's high levels of air and water pollution have worsened in the first half of 2019, reducing the quality of life.

Key Causes of Pollution in Tirana:

Vehicle emissions from old diesel engines. Construction sites and road reconstruction. Extensive urban development. Chaotic public transport system. Heavy traffic congestion.

Impact:

High levels of PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, CO, CO₂, SO₂, NO₂, O₃, and VOCs. Serious health problems for residents. Reduced quality of life. Ranked as one of the most polluted cities in Europe by the 2019 Pollution Index.

**AIR QUALITY IN
TIRANA**

Harta 3. Përqëndrimi i CO₂ në qytetin e Tiranës
Burimi: Co-PLAN & Mësiuokontakt

The CO₂ levels on "Durrës" and "Kavaja" streets are twice the European standard of 350 ppm, reaching 771 ppm. In contrast, areas such as the New Bazaar, "Luigj Gurakuqi" Street, the Tax Directorate, and the "Economic University of Tirana" have recorded CO₂ values close to the EU standard, at 310 ppm.

Harta 4. Përqëndrimi i PM_{2.5} në qytetin e Tiranës
Burimi: Co-PLAN & Mësiuokontakt

The PM_{2.5} dust particle levels are set at 25 (15) µg/m³ by Albanian standards, 25 µg/m³ by European standards, and 10 µg/m³ by WHO standards. Measurements show that near "Petro Nini Luarasi" high school, particle concentrations are double the European standard, reaching 51 µg/m³. Additionally, intersections that exceed EU limits include "Elbasan Street," the roundabout near the Economic University of Tirana, and the small ring road around the city's central pedestrian area.

Harta 5. Përqëndrimi i PM₁₀ në qytetin e Tiranës
Burimi: Co-PLAN & Mësiuokontakt

The concentration of PM₁₀ dust particles has reached up to 101 µg/m³ on "Zogu I Parë" Boulevard, "Dibra" Street, near the American Embassy, the "Economic University," "Petro Nini Luarasi" high school, Municipal Zone No. 5, and "Kavaja" and "Durrës" streets (Albanian standard- 60 µg/m³, EU standard - 40 µg/m³, WHO standard - 20 µg/m³).

What can be done???

The National Air Quality Strategy, approved in 2014, is still the main official document for protecting air quality. However, it is barely implemented across the relevant sectors.

Efforts to reduce pollution at both local and national levels begin with existing legislation. In Albania, Law no. 10431, dated 09.06.2011, "On Environmental Protection," outlines seven objectives for environmental protection.

Data is really important!!!

the municipality has to have it's periodic measures of these indicators.

The final presentations prepared by the students can be accessed here - [PowerPoint Presentation \(greenforcetwinning.net\)](http://greenforcetwinning.net)

Annex 1a – Summer School Call

International Summer School

Communicating Just Green Transitions

Navigating the Path
Sustainable Future

to a

Deadline
for
applicati
on
15.03.20
24

International Summer
School

Communicating Just Green Transitions

Navigating the Path to a Sustainable Future

Deadline for application

15.03.2024

Dates of the Summer School: 13-17 May 2024.

Funded by the
European Union

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Eligible candidates: students enrolled in the Bachelor, Master and PhD programs at the University of Belgrade - Faculty of Geography.

UB-GEF GreenFORCE Team: Aleksandar Djordjevic, Branko Protic, Velimir Secerov, Marija Jetic, Zora Zivanovic, Vladimir Popovic.

Involved universities and institutions: Co-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development (coordinating partner, AL); Polis University (AL); Politecnico di Torino – R3C Responsible Risk Resilience Centre (IT), Nordregio (SE), University of Belgrade – Faculty of Geography (RS) and Center for Economic Analyses Association (MK).

The summer school involves up to 10 selected UB-GEF students within the framework of the HORIZON-WIDERA project "GreenFORCE. Foster Research Excellence for Green Transition in the Western Balkans".

The activity **provides 3 ECTS credits** to the participating students.

Project website: Summer School – GreenFORCE (greenforcetwinning.net)

Contacts: aleksandar.djordjevic@gef.bg.ac.rs ; branko.protic@gef.bg.ac.rs

Funded by the
European Union

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Focus and activities

The summer school in Belgrade is organised jointly by the [University of Belgrade - Faculty of Geography \(UB-GEF\)](#) in Serbia and supported by [Interuniversity Department of Urban and Regional Studies and Planning](#) and the [Interdepartmental Responsible Risk Resilience Centre \(R₃C\)](#) of Politecnico di Torino and is set in the framework of the School of Planning and Design, [Co-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development](#) in Albania as the coordinating partner and the [Center for Economic Analysis Association \(CEA\)](#) in North Macedonia as the regional partner; and [Nordregio](#), a pan-Nordic research organisation based in Sweden.

The urgency of addressing environmental challenges and embracing sustainability has led to an increased focus on educational initiatives such as summer school programs. Communicating the just green transition within such programs is a dynamic and impactful way to instill a sense of responsibility, foster environmental literacy, and empower the next generation to be advocates for positive change.

The students will attend several lectures and working group activities that introduce the challenges they will have to focus on and present possible ways to approach them. Besides the local perspective, students will learn from European and Western Balkans examples and case studies.

They will be supervised and mentored by an international, multi-disciplinary teaching staff during their activity.

Context – Navigating the Path to a Sustainable Future

The imperative for a just green transition (JGT) has become increasingly evident in the face of global challenges such as climate change, resource depletion, and environmental degradation. As societies grapple with the need for sustainable development, effective communication plays a pivotal role in mobilizing public support, shaping policy decisions, and driving meaningful change. Thus is necessary to explore the multifaceted aspects of communicating the just green transition, examining key strategies, challenges, and the role of various stakeholders in fostering a collective commitment to a sustainable future.

To effectively communicate the green transition, it is essential to move beyond traditional environmental narratives and frame the conversation in a way that resonates with diverse audiences. This involves emphasizing the economic, social, and health benefits of sustainability. Communicators should underscore how green initiatives can create jobs, foster innovation, and improve public health, appealing to a broader spectrum of stakeholders, including businesses, policymakers, and the general public.

Successful communication of the JGT requires collaboration among diverse stakeholders. Governments, businesses, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and communities all play integral roles. Stakeholder engagement involves transparent communication, active listening, and the incorporation of diverse perspectives into sustainability initiatives. By fostering a sense of shared responsibility and inclusivity, a coalition for change can be built, promoting a more effective and holistic approach to the JGT.

Technology and innovation are instrumental in advancing the green transition. Communicating the potential of technological solutions, such as renewable energy, circular economies, and sustainable agriculture, is crucial in garnering support. Effectively communicating complex scientific concepts to the public enhances understanding and facilitates public buy-in. Moreover, highlighting success stories and showcasing tangible benefits of green technologies can inspire optimism and confidence in the transition process.

Social networks play a pivotal role in boosting communication about the JGT, offering a powerful platform for disseminating information, fostering engagement, and building a community of environmentally conscious individuals. Leveraging social networks effectively can amplify the impact of sustainability initiatives and

contribute to a broader understanding of the JGT. We can recognize numerous ways in which social networks can enhance communication efforts in promoting a JGT.

A summer school program focuses on the communicating just green transition is a powerful platform for communicating the importance of sustainability to the next generation. With engaging curriculum, integrating interdisciplinary perspectives, leveraging technology, encouraging hands-on experiences, fostering collaboration, empowering advocacy, and showcasing success stories, students will be able to get a transformative learning experience. Through effective communication and hands-on engagement, summer school will play a pivotal role in shaping environmentally conscious and empowered young leaders who will contribute to a sustainable future.

Language

The activity will be exclusively held in English. Please specify your level of English in the application document.

Eligibility Requirements

Eligible students are enrolled in the Bachelor, Master and PhD programs at the University of Belgrade - Faculty of Geography.

ECTS Credits

The participating students will be awarded 3 ECTS credits.

Fees and Obligations

The programme does not require the payment of any fee. The costs covered by the organisation include:

- 5-day intensive summer school in Belgrade with lectures and studio work;
- 1 social dinner;
- 5 lunches and coffee breaks;
- site visits;
- multidisciplinary tutoring from teaching staff from PoliTO, Co-PLAN, U_Polis, Nordregio, UB-GEF and CEA during the academic activities of the summer school.

Participants are required to bring their laptop.

How to participate

Each candidate should fill out the dedicated [Google form](#) and provide, by uploading to the system, the following additional information:

- a motivational letter (max 800 words) written in English;
- a Curriculum Vitae (CV) and/or a portfolio, including the UB-GEF list of exams successfully passed and the achieved marks.

Selection Criteria and Ethics

Candidates will be assessed based on the information provided in the motivation letter and in the CV, or portfolio.

The 10 UB-GEF students will be selected on the basis of the following criteria:

- interest-driving learning in the contents of the Summer School students are applying to (i.e., operationalising just and green transition) based on the motivation letter;
- background and preparation based on the CV and/or the portfolio;
- research skills and attitudes based on the CV and/or the portfolio;

An evaluation committee composed of the UB-GEF staff involved in the teaching activity will assess the candidates.

Ethics disclaimer: The list of selected candidates will ensure a balanced representation of gender. No discrimination will be based on nationality, sexual orientation, or political opinion. UB-GEF will guarantee to maintain a selection process that is fair and equitable, and support informed and responsible decision-making of candidates.

List of Participants

An email will be sent to selected candidates on March the 22nd, 2024. The list will comprise up to 10 selected students + 2 eligible candidates (reserve list).

The ten selected students shall email to both aleksandar.djordjevic@gef.bg.ac.rs and branko.protic@gef.bg.ac.rs to communicate the acceptance of their position by March 25th, 2024. If one of the ten selected students cancels their participation in time, the first eligible candidate in the reserve list will take their place.

Disclaimer

The organization is NOT accountable if the activity is cancelled for any *force majeure* reason.

General timeline

Dates	Before the summer school
1st of March 2024	Launch of the Call for Participation
15th of March 2024	Deadline for students' application
22nd of March 2024	Notification of the results
25th of March 2024	Deadline for acceptance and finalization of the list of participants
	Summer school and after
16th of April 2024	1-day kick-off event (online)
23rd of April 2024	1-day lectures event (online)
24th of April 2024	1-day lectures event (online)
13th-17th of May 2024	Summer school activities in Belgrade
June 2024	Online Final Presentation

GreenFORCE Project

This students' summer school is part of the HORIZON-WIDERA project "GreenFORCE. Foster Research Excellence for Green Transition in the Western Balkans" (HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-02-02). The five partner organisations are [Co-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development](#) in Albania as the coordinating partner; [University of Belgrade - Faculty of Geography \(UB-GEF\)](#) in Serbia and the [Center for Economic Analysis Association \(CEA\)](#) in North Macedonia as the two regional partners; and [Nordregio](#), a pan-Nordic research organisation based in Sweden, together with [Politecnico di Torino \(PoliTO\)](#), in Italy, as the leading EU research institutions. POLIS University (U_Polis) in Albania is the affiliate partner of Co-PLAN.

GreenFORCE aims to foster excellence in the Western Balkans' green transition scientific research and innovation of Co-PLAN (Albania), CEA (North Macedonia), and UB-GEF (Serbia); to enhance their research profile, strengthening the research and management capacities of their staff, and contributing to convergence between Western Balkans and European Union research capacities, as well as to broader policy initiatives for the region. This objective is reached through the twinning partnership of five organisations that work closely to produce territorial knowledge through exploratory research and institutional learning; transfer and exchange knowledge among partner organisations through applying the knowledge management cycle; and engage in networking for sharing, cross-fertilizing and amplifying knowledge at the societal level.

The researchers of the consortium engage in building a joint research project with objectives related to (i) the conceptualisation of green transition in the WB; (ii) the assessment of impacts and costs of just green transition, focusing on components of the pillars of the EU green agenda for the WB; (iii) the proposal of a continuous monitoring and assessment framework on green transition impacts and costs in the WB, to be used by scientists, researchers and policy-makers in facilitating the just green transition.

This summer school is the second of three stand-alone teaching events that contribute to the co-design, co-evaluation, exchange and sharing of the research practice and results conducted in the project. The events are open to students from U_Polis, UB-GEF and PoliTO. Each event will host up to 20 students, of which ten will be from the hosting institution, in this case, UB-GEF. Students attending at least one of the stand-alone teaching events may decide to work more thoroughly on this topic through the development of their master thesis under the supervision of one or more professors involved in the summer school.

For any clarification, please send an email to both aleksandar.djordjevic@gef.bg.ac.rs and branko.protic@gef.bg.ac.rs.

The activity is organized with the support of the University of Belgrade – Faculty of Geography.

Annex 2a – List of Students Selected

Students attending the summer school have agreed on sharing the material

Institution	Surname	Name
UB-GEF	IVANOVIĆ	Bojana
UB-GEF	NIKOLIĆ	Natalija
UB-GEF	BUTRIC	Aleksa
UB-GEF	VUCETIC	Tijana
UB-GEF	BLAGOJEVIĆ	Silvija
UB-GEF	BLAGOJEVIĆ	Anastasija
UB-GEF	ADŽEMOVIĆ	Nikola
UB-GEF	ĐORĐEVIĆ	Mihajlo
UB-GEF	BJELICA	Marko
UB-GEF	RISTIC	Ana
UPolis	RRYCI	Ersi
UPolis	PETI	Kelvi
UPolis	CALA	Skerdi
UPolis	ZENELAJ	Eleonora
UPolis	CELI	Klara
PoliTO	WANG	Liyang
PoliTO	SCHWARTZ	Rob
PoliTO	JINDAL	Nishu Satish
PoliTO	VECCHIO	Michele
PoliTO	JIANG	Guozhen

Annex 3a - The Summer School Agenda

The summer school was organised in three phases. The first phase is the summer school opening, which was organised online to kick off the activity. The second consisted of a five-day working activity held in Turin at the Politecnico di Torino, while the third phase foresaw two post-summer school meetings held online.

Day Zero - Kick-off Meeting, Tuesday 16th April 2024, 9:00 - 14.00 (CEST)

Online

- 09.00 – 09.30: Opening of the summer school and welcoming, **Velimir Secerov**, University of Belgrade – Faculty of Geography,
- 09.30 – 10.00: Presentation of the GreenFORCE project, **Fiona Imami**, Co-PLAN
- 10.00 – 10.30: Introduction to the summer school topic, methodology, agenda and main activities, **Aleksandar Djordjevic, Branko Protic**, University of Belgrade – Faculty of Geography
- 10.30 – 11.00: Partners' Presentations, **GreenFORCE members**
- 11.00 – 11.30: Students' Presentations, **Students**
- 11.30 – 11.45: Break
- 11.45 – 12.45: Setting the context: "Just" Green Transition, **Carlos Tapia**, Nordregio
- 12.45 – 13.30: Setting the context: What About Communication?, **Voislav Zanetic**, communication expert
- 13.30 – 13.45: Final remarks and next steps, **Aleksandar Djordjevic, Branko Protic**, University of Belgrade – Faculty of Geography

Day 1 – lectures event (online), Tuesday 23rd April 2024, 10:00 – 13.15 (CEST)

Online

- 10.00 – 10.15: Opening words for online day 2, **Aleksandar Djordjevic, Branko Protic**, University of Belgrade – Faculty of Geography and partners
- 10.15 – 11.15: Lecture: Towards Just Transition: Navigating Change through Effective Governance and Communication, **Elena Gotovska**, Center for Economic Analyses
- 11.15 – 11.30: Discussion
- 11.30 – 11.45: Coffee break
- 11.45 – 12.45: Lecture: Territorial Resilience and JGT, **Grazia Brunetta and Ombretta Caldarice**, Politecnico di Torino
- 12.45 – 13.00: Discussion
- 13.00 – 13.15: Final remarks and next steps, **Aleksandar Djordjevic, Branko Protic**, University of Belgrade – Faculty of Geography and partners

Day 2 - lectures event (online), Wednesday 24th April 2024, 10:00 - 13.15 (CEST)

Online

- 10.00 – 10.15: Opening words for online day 3, **Aleksandar Djordjevic, Branko Protic**, University of Belgrade – Faculty of Geography and partners
- 10.15 – 11.15: Lecture: Climate literacy and science communication for emergencies – exploring tools, datasets and processes, **Kejt Drahmi**, Co-PLAN
- 11.15 – 11.30: Discussion
- 11.30 – 11.45: Coffee break
- 11.45 – 12.45: Lecture: JGT- Towards urban mobility strategy in Kragujevac, Republic of Serbia, Marija Jetic, University of Belgrade - Faculty of Geography
- 12.45 – 13.00: Discussion
- 13.00 – 13.15: Final remarks and next steps, **Aleksandar Djordjevic, Branko Protic**, University of Belgrade – Faculty of Geography and partners

Day 1 – Monday 13th May 2024, 9:00 - 16.00 (CEST)

Venue: University of Belgrade – Rectorate, Address: Studentski trg, 1, 11000, Belgrade

- 9.00 – 9.15: Opening of the summer school and welcoming, **Velimir Šećerov**, Dean of the UB-GEF, **Aleksandar Đorđević**, GreenFORCE UB-GEF Team Coordinator
- 9.15 – 9.45: Introduction to the summer school (a synthesis), **Aleksandar Đorđević and Branko Protić**, University of Belgrade – Faculty of Geography
- 9.45 – 10.00: Coffee break
- 10.00 – 10.45: Lecture: LOST IN COMMUNICATION (The importance of public communication for science — Introduction), **Vojislav Žanetić**
- 10.45 – 11.00: Break
- 11.00 – 11.45: Lecture: SOCIAL NETWORKING (The role, significance, and means of content communication on social networks in the hyperconnected Society of the Spectacle), **Simona Žikić, PhD and/or Pavle Trifunović**
- 11.45 – 12.00: Subdivision into groups, meeting with the tutors and organisation of the work
- 12:00 – 13:00: Lunch break at Restaurant Mikan
- 13.00 – 16.00: Practice: JUST DOING IT - Work in the classroom under communication tutors' supervision

Day 2 – Tuesday 14th May 2024, 9:00 - 16.00 (CEST)

Venue: University of Belgrade – Rectorate, Address: Studentski trg, 1, 11000, Belgrade

- 9.00 – 9.45: Lecture: POSTED TO BE SPOTTED (Instagram, X, Facebook, other social networks— what is most needed to know?), **Fahri Dashwalli**
- 9.45 – 10.00: Coffee break
- 10.00 – 10.45: Lecture: VENI, VINI, VIDEO (Essentials about making and posting videos on YT, Instagram, and Tik Tok), **Tijana Dedić**
- 10.45 – 11.00: Break

- 11.00 – 11.45: Lecture: FROM CAST TO CAST (Essentials about making podcasts and minicasts), **Luka Bešliagić, PhD**
- 12:00 – 13:00 Lunch break at Restaurant Mikan
- 13.00 – 16.00: Practice: WORK MORE, DO MORE - Work in the classroom under communication tutors' supervision

Day 3 – Wednesday 15th 2024, 9:00 - 16.00 (CEST)

Venue: University of Belgrade – Faculty of Geography, Address: Studentski trg, 3, 11000, Belgrade

- 9.00 – 11.45: Student's visit to the **UNDP**
- 12:00 – 13:00 Lunch break at Restaurant Mikan
- 13.00 – 16.00: Practice and creation: DO-IT-YOURSELF - Work in the classroom under JGT tutors' supervision

Day 4 – Thursday 16th May 2024, 9:00 - 16.00 (CEST)

Venue: University of Belgrade – Faculty of Geography, Address: Studentski trg, 3, 11000, Belgrade

- 9.00 – 11.45: Practice and creation: DO-IT-YOURSELF - Work in the classroom under JGT tutors' supervision
- 12:00 – 13:00 Lunch break at Restaurant Mikan
- 13.00 – 16.00: City tour

Day 5 – Friday 17th May 2024, 9:00 - 16.00 (CEST)

Venue: University of Belgrade – Faculty of Geography, Address: Studentski trg, 3, 11000, Belgrade

- 9.00 – 11.45: Practice and creation: DO-IT-YOURSELF - Work in the classroom under JGT tutors' supervision
- 12:00 – 13:00 Lunch break at Restaurant Mikan
- 13.00 – 15:45 Intermediate presentations of the groups' work, discussion and wrap-up
- 15:45 – 16:00 Final remarks and next steps, **Aleksandar Đorđević and Branko Protić**, University of Belgrade – Faculty of Geography

Day 6 – Final Presentation (online) - Monday 17 June 2024, 10:00 – 14.00 (CEST)

Online

- 10.00 – 13.45: Final presentations of the groups' work and comments from professors and tutors
- 13.45 – 14.00: Final remarks, **Aleksandar Đorđević and Branko Protić**, University of Belgrade – Faculty of Geography

Annex 4a – Teaching Staff

This winter school benefited from the contribution of more than 20 teachers/tutors. The following section provides the list of people involved in with a brief bio each.

Giancarlo Cotella (POLITO UNITE responsible) is associate professor at Politecnico di Torino. His research mainly focuses on European Territorial Governance, in particular on the mutual influence occurring between European Spatial Planning and the spatial governance and planning systems characterising the different Member States. He took active part to several international research projects as ESPON ReSSI, ESPON URRUC, ESPON COMPASS, ESPON SUPER, ESPON METRO, ERASMUS KA2 SPOT and LOTUS and the recently awarded Horizon Europe GreenFORCE and ESPON projects NoStaGeo and TERRES. Since 2023, he serves as Secretary General of the Association of European Schools of Planning.

Erbilin Berisha is assistant professor at Politecnico di Torino. His research focuses on the evolution of Spatial Planning Systems and Territorial Governance in the Western Balkan region in the light of international influence. He is also interested in understanding the geopolitical implications of international initiatives in the region. As research has been involved in numerous international projects like ESPON COMPASS, ESPON SUPER, ESPON SUPER spin-off, ESPON METRO, and more recently is taking an active part in the Horizon Europe GreenFORCE project and in the ESPON projects NoStaGeo and TERRES.

Ombretta Caldarice is Assistant Professor in Urban and Regional Planning at the Interuniversity Department of Regional and Urban Studies and Planning (DIST), Politecnico di Torino. She is a Faculty Affiliate Member of the Responsible Risk Resilience Centre - R3C, Politecnico di Torino. Her research activities focus on the interplay between planning and urban resilience through the lens of planning rules. She has more than ten years of international experience in research, capacity-building, and education on how to make cities more resilient, dealing with the following topics: (i) theories and practices of resilience; (ii) mainstreaming resilience in spatial planning; and (iii) urban codes and techniques for resilience. She is the co-coordinator of the ERASMUS+ Project with the Witwatersrand University Johannesburg on resilience and climate change. She is a member of the scientific committee of the Intensive Training on Urban Resilience (University of Southern of Denmark). She is a member of the Editorial Board of the Springer Book Series "Resilient Cities. Rethinking Urban Transformation."

Kejt Dhrami, Ph.D., is lecturer at Polis University (FPMMU) since 2015. Currently she is coordinator for planning studies in the MSc program, as well as coordinator for spatial planning and GIS in the professional master program. Kejt's academic experiences include subjects such as: planning history; advanced urban development laboratory; final thesis studio; and, previously, planning systems; GIS; urban planning laboratory; urban policies; etc. Alongside her academic engagement, Kejt is also employed as a spatial planning and regional development expert at Co-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development, where she currently manages the Territorial Governance Unit. Her skills extend to GIS database systems management and operationalization. Kejt has managed several initiatives / activities

within international projects, funded by USAID, World Bank, IADSA, UNDP, etc., as well as Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe projects.

Aleksandar Djordjevic works as an associate professor at the University of Belgrade – Faculty of Geography. With a background as spatial planner and GIS analyst, his research revolves around the GIS projects implementation, geospatial analyses, and mapping. Dr Djordjevic coordinated numerous GIS projects on local, regional, and national level in Serbia, as well as within international institutions and companies. His current research interests include the "spatialisation" and visualization of just green transition in the European and Western Balkans' contexts.

Alberto Giacometti is a Senior Research Advisor at Nordregio. He has a background in human geography, regional development, and spatial planning. Alberto works in projects related to regional innovation systems, resilience, governance, and circular economy. His research interests surround the governance and territorial aspects of industrial path creation, including the ongoing just green transition.

Yahya Shaker is a PhD Candidate in the Doctoral Programme in Urban and Regional Development (URD) at the Interuniversity Department of Regional & Urban Studies and Planning (DIST) - Politecnico di Torino and University of Turin, a Co-lecturer of the Urban Planning Module in the City and Territory Studio B Course at (DIST) Politecnico di Torino, and a Teaching Assistant in Urban Design, and Urban Planning Courses at the Department of Architecture and Urban Studies (DASU) at Politecnico di Milano. With an international academic background in the fields of Architecture, Engineering, Urban Planning and Policy Design, he has been dedicated to acquire a multitude of professional experiences in the fields of Strategic Territorial Planning, Urban Planning and Design, Urban and Public Policies, and Spatial Governance, alongside collaborating with various world-class universities and research institutes in the European Union and the United States.

Fiona Imami is a regional development programming, planning & monitoring expert and researcher with a strong educational background in planning and management issues, and a doctoral studies programme in 2021 in the IDAUP (Polis / Ferrara) program. With a professional experience of around 10 years, Fiona has significantly contributed to central and local government institutions in Albania, specializing in strategic document preparation and administrative staff capacity building. Over the years she has worked especially in project implementation and management for local and regional planning and programming, including here drafting of territorial plans, economic development strategies, regional and national programmes etc. funded by various international institutions such as USAID, ADA, SDC, GIZ and UNDP. As a researcher Fiona's current interests span over fostering green transition initiatives, in which she's involved in EU Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe projects funded projects. Additionally, Fiona's academic rigor is sustained by her continuous engagement as lecturer at Polis university and her commitment in authoring and co-authoring a list of scientific and policy papers.

Vojislav Žanetić is a marketing communication consultant, professional copywriter, and university lecturer. Creator of communication campaigns for products, services, industries, and trade; brand and advertising content maker with 40 years of experience in over 200 campaigns. Appeared at more than 100 public lectures and debates in the field of market communications. Apart from his work in the field of market communications, he is also known to the public in Serbia as a satirist and columnist.

Fahri Dashwali is a distinguished lecturer at the Faculty of Media and Communication, where he shares his extensive knowledge of Google advertising and social media usage. At the same time, as the director of Fast Digital in Dubai and a consultant for four American franchises in the fitness and wellness industry, Fahri applies his expertise in digital marketing to improve the online presence and communication of brands. His approach to digital strategies is characterized by understanding the needs of target groups and creativity in content creation. With over ten years of experience, Fahri has successfully positioned himself as a mentor and lecturer, contributing not only to the growth and development of digital marketing but also to the education of a new generation of experts in this field.

Luka Bešlagić is an Associate professor and Head of the Department at the Faculty of Media and Communications in Belgrade, with more than 10 years of experience in lecturing, teaching media studies, film, and contemporary art. Through numerous public lectures and trainings he transferred applicable knowledge as a practical framework needed for improvement of projects and ongoing communication activities of those engaged in media industries. Corporate clients in manufacturing and services industries (e.g. energy production, banking), as well as public institution (e.g. arts and culture), used his output/outcome-oriented lectures and trainings in order to advance applied methodology and communication skills. Apart of academic and consultant's experience, he disseminates his media and communication expertise via public media appearance, such as TV, radio, Internet, film and photography festivals, etc. His theoretical study Theories of Experimental Textual Production has been awarded for contribution to the innovative practice in education.

Marija Simojlović is a Teaching assistant at the Department of Media and Communications. She has experience working in the IT industry, agile startup companies, and cultural institutions, where she led successful marketing campaigns, created textual, visual, and audio-visual content for social networks, and implemented effective internal and external communication strategies. She participated in the organization of many workshops and educational programs for young people.

Pavle Trifunovic is a Belgrade-based communications specialist with a strong background in journalism, production, graphic design, and digital marketing. She holds both a Bachelor's and Master's degree in Journalism and Communications from the Faculty of Media and Communications in Belgrade. In addition to her formal education, she participated in seminars on anthropology, sociology, and psychology at the Petnica Research Station, where she also presented her research at the 2018 conference on the topic "Outing as a Rite of Passage." He combines creative thinking with strong analytical skills. Her professional journey spans roles as a teaching assistant at the Faculty of Media and Communications and as a production assistant for the Belgrade Dance Festival, TV Al Jazeera, and TV

Nova S. He has also worked extensively in creative marketing, graphic design, and social media management for organizations such as Superdot Creative Marketing, Hali Gali Festival, and the Kišobran NGO. Her design and branding work includes projects for high-profile clients such as professional driver Dušan Borković, the social hubs "Zaokret" and "Sprat," the Stenaraonline vintage shop, Velvet Festival in Croatia, Yandex, KC Grad, and the Belgrade Jazz Festival.

Simona Žikić holds a Ph.D. in Communications and Public Relations from the Faculty of Media and Communications in Belgrade, Serbia. Her doctoral dissertation focused on "Aspects of Communication in Contemporary Team Leadership." In addition to her academic credentials, Dr. Žikić has extensive training in career development and business skills, both domestically and internationally. She is a certified trainer and advisor for multinational companies and has authored several manuals in business communications, strategic planning, and public relations. Dr. Žikić is a highly experienced project leader, having spearheaded numerous scientific and applied projects. She is also actively involved in humanitarian initiatives, having launched a significant number of campaigns. Dr. Žikić's professional experience is multifaceted. She currently serves as the PR and Marketing Manager at the Faculty of Media and Communications, while also holding a faculty appointment as a lecturer in Communications and Public Relations. Previously, she held a research position at the Institute of Philosophy and Social Theory at the University of Belgrade.

Tijana Dedić currently pursuing a Master's Degree in Creative Industries and serving as a teaching assistant. Additionally, a member of the marketing team at the Faculty of Media and Communication. With an extensive marketing experience, her expertise encompasses content creation for social media platforms, conceptualization of creative campaigns, video production, editing, graphic design, and animation. As a content creator, she has been a part of numerous projects and events such as conferences, seminars, festivals and workshops.

Zoran Pešić completed BA (hons) degree in Digital marketing at the Faculty of Media and Communications, where he currently works as a marketing manager. Rich experience in various aspects of marketing, including content writing, social media management, and community management. Former teaching associate. Admin and community manager of various groups and communities, fostering engagement and building relationships with members. As an enthusiastic photographer, he captures moments that resonate with audiences, whether it's a product photo, an event, or a captivating landscape.

Part 2 – Winter School in Tirana, Albania

International Winter School

Scaling down Green Transition

Co-creating Nature-Based Solutions at the neighborhood level

7. Summer School Organisation

The Winter School in Tirana was organized by Co-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development and POLIS University, in the framework of the GreenFORCE project, and supported by the Interuniversity Department of Urban and Regional Studies and Planning and the Interdepartmental Responsible Risk Resilience Centre (R3C) of Politecnico di Torino in Italy; the Center for Economic Analyses Association (CEA) in North Macedonia; the University of Belgrade - Faculty of Geography (UB-GEF) in Serbia; and Nordregio, a pan-Nordic research organisation based in Sweden. It brought together students from the participating institutions to explore how Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) can support just and localized green transitions at the neighborhood level.

With a strong focus on co-creation and hands-on learning, participants engaged in lectures, in-field assessments, and collaborative design work addressing the environmental performance of three target neighborhoods in Tirana. Students applied advanced environmental tools—such as ENVI-met simulations and ecosystem service evaluations—and collaborated directly with local stakeholders and municipal representatives. Guided by a multidisciplinary international team, the Winter School provided a valuable opportunity to test low-cost, high-impact strategies for improving neighbourhood livability and resilience.

The program ran in three phases: an online kick-off (28 January 2025), two days of virtual lectures (5 & 12 February 2025), a five-day intensive workshop in Tirana (17–21 February 2025), and a final online feedback session on 27th March 2025. Twenty students from Politecnico di Torino, the University of Belgrade, and POLIS University participated in the winter school.

7.1 The Topic “Scaling down Green Transition - Co-creating Nature-Based Solutions at the neighborhood level”

As the need for a just green transition (JGT) becomes more urgent across regions facing climate vulnerabilities and urbanization pressures, the Winter School in Tirana focused on a fundamental question: **How can we translate ambitious green objectives into localized, actionable solutions at the neighborhood level?** Recognizing that meaningful transformation often begins within communities, the program addressed the importance of scaling down the green transition and engaging citizens in the design of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) to improve environmental performance and social cohesion in urban areas.

Participants explored the intersection of spatial justice, environmental equity, and participatory urban planning, engaging in site-based analysis in Tirana’s pre-communist neighborhoods. Through lectures, fieldwork, and collaborative scenario-building exercises, students assessed real-life urban challenges such as heat island effects, poor air quality, flooding risks, and limited access to green public spaces. Their work emphasized how nature-based and low-cost interventions can act as catalysts for improving resilience while fostering inclusive, just development.

By working directly with local stakeholders and municipal representatives, and employing innovative environmental modeling tools like ENVI-met and ecosystem service assessments, the Winter School highlighted how just green transitions require context-sensitive planning, interdisciplinary collaboration, and a deep understanding of social realities on the ground. Ultimately, the Winter School demonstrated that effective, equitable green transition requires more than top-down strategies—it demands grounded, community-driven innovation. By anchoring green transition strategies in specific local contexts, and by empowering a new generation of planners, designers, and researchers with both the tools and the mindset to think systemically and act locally, the Winter School played a critical role in advancing the broader mission of the GreenFORCE project and the EU’s Green Agenda for the Western Balkans. It also served as a space for dialogue, experimentation, and learning—where theory met practice, and where the seeds of future sustainable urban transformation were planted.

The organization of the summer school in Belgrade followed three main steps (see Figure 1): (i) Step1 - co-design of the summer school topic with partners and preparation of the call lead by Co-PLAN and POLIS University; Step 2 -launching of the call and students’ selection; Step 3 - the summer school implementation.

Figure 2 - 2nd Stand-alone Teaching Event in Belgrade: timetable and main steps

Summer School Topic Definition

As the lead organizer and host institution for the Winter School in Tirana, Co-PLAN, in close cooperation with POLIS University, initiated a participatory and consultative process to determine the most suitable thematic focus for this final teaching event under the GreenFORCE project. Drawing upon insights gathered during earlier project activities and partner workshops, Co-PLAN proposed a preliminary set of potential themes aligned with the overarching aim of fostering Just Green Transitions

(JGT) in the Western Balkans. This list was then shared with all GreenFORCE partners—Politecnico di Torino, University of Belgrade - Faculty of Geography (UB-GEF), Nordregio, and the Center for Economic Analyses Association (CEA)—who collectively contributed to refining and elaborating the proposed topics.

The selection process was guided by four main criteria:

1. **Thematic Coherence with JGT Objectives:** The chosen topic—scaling down the green transition to the neighborhood level through Nature-Based Solutions (NBS)—was selected for its strong alignment with the core principles of justice, inclusion, and environmental sustainability underpinning the JGT agenda.
2. **Relevance at Multiple Scales:** The topic was considered highly relevant to both the national context in Albania and the broader Western Balkans region, particularly in light of the rapid urban development and environmental challenges facing many cities, including Tirana.
3. **Capacity and Expertise within the Consortium:** The partners jointly recognized the depth of knowledge and applied research experience available within the GreenFORCE network on topics such as NBS, environmental performance, participatory planning, and urban resilience. This ensured that the Winter School would provide high-quality mentorship and academic value to participating students.
4. **Local Replicability and Transformative Potential:** The selected topic was also favored for its practical applicability in real urban settings, particularly in transitioning pre-communist neighborhoods of Tirana. It was seen as an opportunity to co-design solutions that could inform future planning approaches, inspire municipal action, and be scaled or replicated across other cities in the region.
5. **Interdisciplinary Learning Potential:** The topic was selected for its ability to foster cross-disciplinary dialogue among students and faculty from diverse academic backgrounds—urban planning, architecture, environmental science, geography, and engineering. Nature-Based Solutions and neighborhood-level transitions inherently require integrative thinking, making the topic ideal for a collaborative and holistic learning experience.
6. **Engagement with Stakeholders and Policy Relevance:** The selected theme enables direct interaction with municipal authorities, local stakeholders, and communities, offering students a grounded understanding of how sustainability policies are implemented (or challenged) on the ground. This relevance to current urban policy debates enhances both the pedagogical and practical value of the Winter School.
7. **Alignment with Ongoing Research and Institutional Strategies:** The topic also aligns with the long-term research agenda and institutional priorities of the hosting universities and partners—particularly POLIS University's strategic focus on green urbanism and Co-PLAN's involvement in place-based sustainability research. This ensured continuity and strategic relevance within each institution's educational and research frameworks.

In addition, the decision to focus on neighborhood-level green transition strategies was further supported by the research case developed in Albania under the GreenFORCE project, which specifically

explored net-zero transitions in post-communist residential blocks. This provided a rich contextual and empirical foundation for the Winter School, enabling students to build their NBS proposals upon existing findings and insights into the spatial, environmental, and socio-economic dynamics of Tirana's urban fabric.

Moreover, POLIS University's dual academic strength in urban planning and environmental management created an ideal institutional setting for delivering this topic. The interdisciplinary expertise available—spanning design, spatial systems, and ecological thinking—ensured that students could benefit from a comprehensive learning environment where theory and practice were integrated to address real-world urban challenges..

Call Preparation

POLIS University, with collaboration of Co-PLAN has coordinated the preparation of the call in conjunction with all partners involved. As Annex 1b shows, a document was prepared including some info regarding among the others:

- The focus and main activities;
- The context and the rationale;
- Eligibility Requirements, language, ECTS credits;
- Selection Criteria and Ethics.

The Launch of the summer school

The call has been launched simultaneously by each academic partner (POLIS, UBGeF and POLITO) and communicated by the project website at the following link:

<https://greenforcetwinning.net/2025/01/06/international-winter-school-in-tirana-scaling-down-green-transition-co-creating-nature-based-solutions-at-the-neighbourhood-level/>

Student Selection

Students have been selected by each institution according to the following criteria (see annex 2 – list of students): The selection aimed to ensure academic merit, alignment with the Winter School's thematic focus, and balanced participation. The final list of selected students is presented in Annex 2.

The selection was based on the following criteria:

- **Interest and Motivation:** Demonstrated interest in the content of the Winter School—specifically in scaling down the Just Green Transition at the neighborhood level through Nature-Based Solutions—based on a well-argued motivation letter.
- **Academic Background and Preparation:** Relevant academic profile and study progress, particularly in urban planning, environmental management, architecture, construction engineering, or energy efficiency, as reflected in the CV, academic transcript, and/or portfolio.

- **Research Skills and Attitudes:** Demonstrated capacity for critical thinking, problem-solving, and interdisciplinary engagement, based on past academic and/or project experience outlined in the CV or portfolio.

The winter school activity is explained in the following section.

8. Winter school main activity conducted

8.1 Kick Off & Online Lecture Series

The GreenFORCE Winter School officially kickstarted on January 28, 2025, with a warm welcome from Prof. Merita Toska, Vice Rector of POLIS University, who highlighted the School's goal of bringing green transition closer to students through collaborative and practice-based learning. Dr. Fiona Imami and Dr. Anila Bejko from Co-PLAN introduced the GreenFORCE project and its key milestones, setting the context for the School within broader regional efforts to promote research excellence in the Western Balkans.

Following this, GreenFORCE partners Prof. Giancarlo Cotella (Politecnico di Torino), Alberto Giacometti (Nordregio), Dr. Vesna Garvanlieva (CEA), and Dr. Aleksandar Djordjevic (UB-GEF) shared institutional perspectives on how each partner contributes to advancing just green transitions through research, teaching, and policy engagement.

To help participants connect, a "Tour de Table" session allowed all students to introduce themselves and their academic backgrounds and Dr. Kejt Dhrami from Co-PLAN followed then outlined the Winter Schools structure, including key dates, activities, and expected outcomes. The session closed with an open Q&A, offering space for clarifications and community building.

Online Lecture Day 1 (5 February 2025)

The first online lecture session was envisaged to prepare students for the theoretical dimensions of just green transitions and nature-based approaches. The following lectures were held during the first online lecture series:

- Dr. Kejt Dhrami (Co-PLAN) began the day with the lecture "What Does It Mean to Be Green?", which offered a critical framework for understanding green urbanism. She unpacked the meanings of being "green" in the context of urban resilience, biodiversity, and decarbonization—connecting theoretical concepts such as ecosystem services, urban green infrastructure, and nature-based solutions with real-world policy frameworks like the EU Green Deal and the Green Agenda for the Western Balkans
- Hedda Thomson and Alberto Giacometti (Nordregio) delivered a compelling lecture on "Harnessing Nature: The Promise and Practice of Nature-Based Solutions." They traced the origins of NbS, introduced the IUCN standards, and showcased global case studies—including urban drainage in Bogotá and community gardens in Stockholm—to demonstrate how NbS can address societal challenges through both top-down and bottom-up approaches

- To conclude the day, Prof. Ass. Anja Randelović (UB-GEF) presented “Nature-Based Solutions to Healthier Cities,” linking NbS to public health and quality of life. Her talk emphasized how urban design can integrate ecological functions to reduce stress, heat, and pollution in dense urban areas, especially in the Western Balkans context.

The screenshot shows a Zoom meeting with several participants. The presentation slides are visible in the background. The first slide is titled 'Urban resilience' and discusses the popularity of urban resilience in academic and policy discourse. The second slide is titled 'Evolution of Nature-based solution' and shows a timeline from 1980s to 2020s, highlighting the shift from traditional worldviews to nature-based solutions. The third slide is titled 'Characteristics of NBS in urban places' and lists several key features such as small-scale systems, multiple purposes, and benefits for people and nature.

The session ended with an interactive Q&A where students reflected on how NbS could be implemented in their home cities and future design projects.

Online Lecture Day 2 (12 February 2025)

The second online lecture day deepened the discussion around the economic, strategic, and climate-related dimensions of NbS. The following lectures were held during the second online lecture series:

- Dr. Ombretta Caldarice (Politecnico di Torino) opened with “Nature-Based Solutions for Urban Resilience and Green Transition: Setting the Scene.” She introduced the concept of Urban Climate Shelters (UCS) as a planning tool to tackle heatwaves and social inequity. Drawing on EU-funded case studies, she highlighted how collaborative governance, co-creation, and inclusive narratives are critical to embedding NbS into urban planning
- Dr. Vesna Garvanlieva Andonova (CEA) followed with a practical session titled “Cost-Benefit Analysis: Understanding the Economic Value of NbS.” She introduced CBA as a vital method to assess the viability of green solutions compared to grey infrastructure. The session provided step-by-step insights into applying CBA for evaluating co-benefits such as carbon sequestration, water retention, and public health, especially when working with limited data
- Dr. Klodjan Xhexhi (POLIS University) closed the day with an applied lecture on “Urban Heat Islands in Tirana: Analysis and Potential Solutions.” Using field data collected across four

neighborhoods, he demonstrated how surface temperatures, CO₂ concentrations, and humidity levels vary across the city and discussed low-cost interventions such as increasing green cover and using reflective materials to mitigate UHI effects

Data Collection Process

4 Rounds of Measurements:

- February 23, 2023
- March 23, 2023
- April 24, 2023
- May 29, 2023

Day	Temperature on the ground (°C)			humidity (%)	
	Asphalt	Sidewalk	Greenery	(ppm)	(%)
01					
02					
03					

Together, these online sessions built a strong theoretical and analytical foundation for the in-person fieldwork to follow in Tirana, helping students understand both the environmental and socio-economic dimensions of just green transition strategies.

8.2 In-presence Winter School in Tirana

The in-person segment of the GreenFORCE Winter School brought together students, lecturers, and experts at POLIS University in Tirana for an intensive, hands-on exploration of how Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) can support just green transitions at the neighborhood level. Over five days, participants engaged in a rich blend of lectures, site visits, group work, and stakeholder interactions, structured to link theory with practice in the Albanian urban context.

Day 1 - Framing the Context & Launching the Fieldwork

The week opened with welcoming remarks by POLIS University representatives and Co-PLAN staff, followed by an introductory lecture by Dr. Doriana Musai on Tirana's recent urban transformations and planning challenges. Dr. Kejt Dhrami then presented the specific case studies and methodological approach, setting the stage for the weeks collaborative design work. Students were grouped into multidisciplinary teams and introduced to their assigned neighborhoods through an experimental landscape exercise led by Silvi Jano and Kejt Dhrami, encouraging them to critically observe the local environment through the lens of urban ecology and social equity.

Day 2 - Site Visits & Data Collection

Participants took part in a guided study tour of Tirana, exploring recent urban interventions and learning about the city's adaptation challenges and opportunities. Each team then conducted on-site observations and interviews in their assigned neighborhoods—Ali Demi, Twenty-One, and the Technological Park area—collecting environmental and social data to inform their NBS proposals. The fieldwork allowed students to engage with residents, assess microclimatic conditions, and identify underutilized public spaces suitable for intervention.

Day 3 - Technical Deep-Dives & Scenario Development

Back at POLIS University, the day opened with a lecture by Silvi Jano on the use of indigenous plant species in green roofs, followed by Dr. Ledian Bregasi who introduced students to ENVI-met simulations and environmental modeling tools to support NBS planning. In the afternoon, students began working in their groups under faculty supervision, using the collected data to build preliminary design concepts that addressed site-specific challenges like urban heat, flooding, and limited green infrastructure.

Day 4 - Institutional Engagement & Collaborative Work

The fourth day featured a visit to the Municipality of Tirana, where students met with staff from the Directorate of Sustainable Development and Natural Emergencies. This provided valuable insight into how environmental strategies are developed and implemented at the local level. In the afternoon, students reconvened at Destil Creative Hub to refine their proposals, supported by feedback from lecturers and professionals, integrating institutional priorities with community needs and green transition principles.

Day 5 - Presentations, Peer Review & Closing

On the final day, teams presented their neighborhood-specific proposals in a "Pitching of Ideas" session. Their projects addressed issues such as urban heat island reduction, stormwater management, biodiversity enhancement, and community activation. A co-selection process allowed both jury members and peers to vote for the most innovative and feasible proposal. The day concluded with a certificate awarding ceremony, final reflections, and a networking cocktail—offering a celebratory closure to an engaging, interdisciplinary learning experience.

8.3 Online Final presentations

The GreenFORCE Winter School concluded with a final online presentation session on 24 March 2025, bringing together students, mentors, and partner institutions for a reflective and celebratory closing. Each of the three student groups—assigned to the Ali Demi, Twenty-One, and Technological Park neighborhoods in Tirana—presented their Nature-Based Solution (NBS) proposals, developed through field research, modeling, and collaborative design during the in-person week in February.

The presentations showcased a diversity of interventions aimed at enhancing environmental resilience and social inclusivity—including green corridors, pocket parks, shaded pedestrian routes, permeable surfaces for stormwater management, and urban agriculture initiatives. The students used a combination of ENVI-met simulations, ecosystem service mapping, and stakeholder insights to justify the feasibility and impact of their proposals.

Following each presentation, members of the GreenFORCE academic team provided detailed feedback and highlighted the innovation, relevance, and local adaptability of the students' work. The session concluded with a round of reflections from both students and faculty, emphasizing the transformative value of hands-on, place-based learning and cross-border collaboration in tackling just green transitions at the neighborhood scale.

9. Summer school main results and outputs

The GreenFORCE Winter School in Tirana concluded with a compelling set of results, demonstrating how neighborhood-scale Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) can support just green transitions in post-communist urban areas. Over the course of five intensive days in Tirana—and through weeks of preparatory and follow-up work—the GreenFORCE Winter School demonstrated how a new generation of urban practitioners can co-create actionable solutions for just green transitions at the neighborhood scale. Students from Albania, Serbia, Italy, and beyond were grouped into interdisciplinary teams and tasked with developing two Nature-Based Solution (NBS) scenarios per neighborhood across three urban case studies in Tirana: Ali Demi, 21 Dhjetori, and Ex-Technological Park. Their mission was clear: analyze existing conditions, engage the community, and propose realistic, cost-effective NBS strategies that improve environmental performance, social inclusion, and climate resilience—building directly on previous GreenFORCE research on net-zero transition in post-communist neighborhoods.

Each teams work culminated in a set of well-researched, site-specific scenarios, underpinned by ecosystem service assessments, stakeholder consultations, and grounded fieldwork. Below is a detailed look into the results by neighborhood:

Neighbourhood 1: Ali Demi / Revitalizing with Green and Blue Infrastructure

The first team worked in the Ali Demi neighborhood, a mixed-use area with post-communist apartment blocks, suffering from poor water infrastructure, neglected public spaces, and a lack of accessible communal areas.

- **Scenario 1 - Community-Centered Greening and Social Revitalization** :The students proposed a thoughtful revitalization plan that sought to activate social spaces through greenery, transforming underutilized corners into small pocket parks and public gathering areas. A central idea was to open schoolyards to the community after hours, integrating seating, modular shading structures, and safe green surfaces. They also proposed green facade installations using resident-maintained planters to reduce heat and improve air quality. Permeable parking lots and pedestrian-friendly pavements completed the intervention, striking a balance between ecological gain and daily functionality.
- **Scenario 2 - Rainwater as a Resource**: This scenario zoomed in on water-sensitive urban design, tackling rainwater mismanagement through a series of smart, nature-based solutions. Highlights included redirecting rainwater to tree pits and bioswales, converting unused surfaces into green parking zones, and launching a rainwater collection pilot in partnership with a local elementary school, aimed at irrigating a proposed community garden. The combination of ecological function and resident participation embodied the just transition principle of inclusiveness and co-ownership.

Key Output: A dual-strategy intervention plan combining water-sensitive design and community co-creation, supported by cost-benefit calculations on air quality, flood mitigation, and energy savings.

The team estimated 1,500 EUR in annual energy savings and improved stormwater retention across the site.

Neighbourhood 2: 21 Dhjetori/ Rebalancing Mobility and Ecology

The second team took on the 21 Dhjetori neighborhood, one of Tirana's most traffic-congested residential areas. Dominated by impermeable surfaces, illegal parking, and poor pedestrian safety, the area also suffers from inadequate green space and localized flooding.

- **Scenario 1 - Enhancing Water Management:** The students addressed the chronic urban flooding and runoff issues by designing a system of rain gardens, permeable pavements, and a central urban mini-park equipped with stormwater filtration features. A key proposal was the strategic greening of parking zones, combining practical needs with ecological enhancement. Through modeling, the team demonstrated how these measures would reduce surface runoff while increasing local biodiversity.
- **Scenario 2 - Public Space for All:** The second scenario emphasized functional and inclusive public space design, guided by stakeholder feedback. Key interventions included designated playgrounds, separate dog parks, shaded rest areas, and safer pedestrian access routes. The team also proposed the creation of community gardens managed by residents, thereby promoting long-term stewardship and participation.

Key Output: A detailed urban design masterplan integrating both grey-to-green conversion and socially inclusive design elements, coupled with a quantified assessment of ecosystem service gains—including improved stormwater infiltration, better thermal comfort, and up to 5,000 EUR/year in public health and energy-related benefits.

Neighbourhood 3: Parku Teknologjik/ A Testbed for Energy and Environmental Renewal

The third team focused on the Ex-Technological Park neighborhood, a compact, aging residential area severely affected by environmental degradation, poor insulation, and socio-economic vulnerability. With little greenery and no structured water management system, the area epitomizes the challenges of post-communist urbanism.

- **Scenario 1 - The “Breathing Wall” Strategy:** This low-cost, high-impact proposal centered around vertical greening, transforming facades into passive cooling and air-purifying systems. In addition, the team proposed permeable pathways, urban gardens, and micro pocket parks to reduce dust, heat, and promote social interaction. The aim was to create immediate, visible improvements with minimal displacement or cost.
- **Scenario 2 - Blue-Green Infrastructure for Long-Term Resilience:** The second scenario took a broader, long-term view, proposing a network of green roofs, bioswales, tree corridors, and a rainwater harvesting system that collectively tackled multiple environmental and social dimensions. The team produced detailed ecosystem service assessments, showing how their plan could deliver €4,500 in annual co-benefits—ranging from energy efficiency to flood protection and urban cooling.

Key Output: A strategic dual-scenario package designed for phased implementation, with scenario 1 serving as an entry-level transformation and scenario 2 providing a blueprint for structural regeneration aligned with the EU Green Deal and climate adaptation goals.

Through these scenario-based interventions, each student team addressed not only the ecological and spatial challenges of their assigned neighborhood but also the underlying social dynamics and community needs. Their proposals demonstrated how low-cost, nature-based strategies can generate high-impact environmental, health, and social benefits when co-designed with local context in mind. Beyond academic value, the Winter School outcomes offer actionable insights for municipalities, urban planners, and policy-makers working toward just and climate-resilient cities.

International Winter School

Scaling down Green Transition

Co-creating Nature-Based Solutions at the neighborhood level

Deadline for application

20/01/2025

Dates of the Winter School:

17-21 February 2025

Location:

Tirana, Albania, Polis University

Eligible Candidates:

Up to 10 Students enrolled in POLIS University (3-5 years of study)

Eligible students include those enrolled in the Faculty of Planning, Environment and Urban Management. Also, students from the Faculty of Architecture and Design, especially those in the Energy Efficiency, Construction Engineering, and Architecture curriculums, are encouraged to participate in the workshop.

ECTS:

The activity provides 3 ECTS credits to the participating students.

POLIS University & Co-PLAN organising committee: Fiona Imami, Kejt Dhrami, Anila Bejko, Merita Toska, Elona Karafili, Enkela Poro

Partner Universities and Institutions

Co-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development (coordinating partner, AL); POLIS University (AL); Politecnico di Torino – R3C Responsible Risk Resilience Centre (IT); Nordregio (SE); University of Belgrade – Faculty of Geography (RS); and Center for Economic Analyses Association (MK).

Focus and Activities

The Winter School in Tirana is organised jointly by [Co-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development](#) and [POLIS University](#) and supported by the [Interuniversity Department of Urban and Regional Studies and Planning](#) and the [Interdepartmental Responsible Risk Resilience Centre \(R3C\)](#) of Politecnico di Torino. The school is supported by the [Center for Economic Analysis Association \(CEA\)](#) in North Macedonia, the [University of Belgrade, Faculty of Geography](#); as the regional partners, and [Nordregio](#), a pan-Nordic research organisation based in Sweden.

The Winter School emphasises Just Green Transitions (JGT), which offers students a dynamic platform to explore, design, and implement localised solutions that align with the SDGs, the EU Green Deal, and the Green Agenda for the Western Balkans. Through the program, participants will enhance their technical competencies using advanced **environmental modelling** and **ecosystem service assessment tools**, enabling them to evaluate and improve neighbourhood-level environmental performance. Additionally, they will develop **practical problem-solving abilities** by working collaboratively in teams to design Nature-Based Solutions tailored to real cases. The program will also enhance the student's **community engagement skills** as they interact directly with local stakeholders in target neighbourhoods. Participants will refine their strategic decision-making capabilities through the on-site workshop, a series of online and in-person lectures, a scenario-building game, meetings with local authorities, etc., learning to balance cost-effectiveness with social and environmental benefits. Students will be supervised and mentored by an international, multi-disciplinary teaching staff during their activity.

Prepare for an exciting, fast-paced event that brings a unique localised Balkan perspective to the Green Transition discussion!

Rationale and Context

The global urgency for sustainable growth and climate resilience has brought the green transition to the forefront of policy, planning, and community action. While much of the discourse focuses on national and international strategies, meaningful implementation often occurs at more minor scales—within neighbourhoods and communities where people directly experience the impacts of environmental degradation and climate change. Translating broad green transition objectives into localised, actionable initiatives is essential for fostering tangible climate change. Yet, communities often face difficulties incorporating top-down policy changes into their daily livelihood.

This Winter School focuses on **scaling down the green transition** to the neighbourhood level, emphasising the critical role of communities in co-creating solutions. By designing Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), which use natural processes to address environmental, social, and economic challenges, this program seeks to demonstrate how neighbourhoods can drastically improve energy and climate performance, thus becoming true catalysts for change!

Why work at the neighbourhood level?

Neighborhoods are the closest spatial and social units to individuals. Interventions at this scale offer visible, direct benefits, such as improved air quality, reduced urban heat islands, enhanced biodiversity, and better social cohesion. The Winter School will focus on three target neighbourhoods in Tirana, with particular socio-demographic characteristics. Extensive research on urban environmental performance and land development in

the three target neighbourhoods shows immense potential and feasibility for renovation of the buildings to become as close to net zero as possible. However, this is not enough. Environmental performance at the neighbourhood level is not solely related to the renovation but also to smaller-scale, nature-based interventions in the public space between buildings. This will be the focus of the Winter School.

By engaging at the neighbourhood level, participants will experience meaningful citizen participation. Residents have intimate knowledge of local challenges and opportunities, making them invaluable contributors to co-designed solutions. The participatory approach aligns with the principles of a just green transition, ensuring no one is left behind. These neighbourhoods will serve as experimental hubs for testing and refining green transition strategies focused on low-cost, scalable initiatives in other, more complex, urban realities.

Measuring Environmental Performance

Measuring environmental performance at the neighbourhood level is crucial in identifying challenges and opportunities to reach the localised SDG targets and EU Green Deal milestones. This involves employing a mix of quantitative and qualitative methods, such as field observations, environmental modelling through GIS-linked software, ecosystem service evaluations, and in-site assessments of different parameters like air quality, urban heat islands, rainwater management, and biodiversity. These methods provide valuable insights into the baseline conditions of neighbourhoods. However, challenges arise from data limitations, such as the availability and accuracy of local environmental data.

During the Winter School in Tirana, participants will work in multidisciplinary teams, navigating the abovementioned challenges and using alternative methods for assessing and observing environmental performance. In the end, each team will provide a design solution for increasing the environmental livability of the areas, tackling the mitigation of flooding, improving air and water quality, reducing urban heat islands, reducing energy savings, enhancing public spaces, etc.

The International Winter School invites students from Politecnico di Torino, University of Belgrade - Faculty of Geography, and Polis University to explore the concept of a Just Green Transition at the neighbourhood level. This immersive program combines theory, practical fieldwork, and design exercises, focusing on developing and implementing Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) to address environmental challenges.

Participants will work with three Albanian neighbourhoods to assess their environmental performance using observation, ENVI-met simulations, and ecosystem service evaluations. The outcomes will inform the co-design of innovative, cost-effective NBS tailored to local community needs. To further engagement, the Winter School will include a collaborative game to develop and refine optimal transition scenarios for these communities.

Language Requirements

The activity will be exclusively held in English. Please specify your English level in the application documents.

Academic Requirements

Eligible students are enrolled in the “Faculty of Planning, Environment and Urban Management” or “Faculty of Architecture and Design” in their 3rd, 4th, and 5th year of studies. We encourage the participation of students from multi-disciplinary curriculums, including Urban Planning, Energy Efficiency, Construction Engineering and Architecture. Younger students attending 1st or 2nd year will be allowed to participate in extraordinary cases if

high academic performance is proved, exceeding the results of the other applicants. The committee reserves the right to hold verbal interviews with the candidates before the notification of the final results.

IMPORTANT

To be eligible, each student must verify and confirm that they are part of POLIS University and will commit to attending the Winter School schedules full time. Failing to attend the online and on-site workshops and activities will revoke the possibility of obtaining the winter school certificate and be awarded the respective credits.

ECTS Credits

The participating students will be awarded **3 ECTS** credits.

Fees and Requirements

The programme does not require the payment of any fee. The costs covered by the Winter School include:

- 5-day intensive Winter School in Tirana, with lectures and studio work;
- 1 social dinner;
- 5 lunches and coffee breaks;
- logistics costs for site visits
- multidisciplinary tutoring from teaching staff from POLITO, Co-PLAN, U_Polis, Nordregio, UB-GEF and CEA during the academic activities of the winter school.

Any personal expenses, extra meals and other costs not specifically mentioned above (i.e. extra commodities, travel to Polis University, etc.) are not included. Participants are required to cover their expenses and must bring their laptops.

How to Participate

Each candidate should fill out the dedicated [Google FORM](#) and provide, by uploading to the system, the following additional information:

- a photocopy of your passport (the page with pictures, personal info, and expiration date) is needed.
- a signed self-declaration confirming that you fully commit to participating in Winter School Activities.
- a motivational letter (max 800 words) written in English;
- a Curriculum Vitae (CV) and/or a portfolio;
- a list of exams successfully passed and the marks achieved for the academic year 2023-2024.

Selection Criteria and Ethics

Candidates will be assessed based on the information provided in the motivation letter and the CV or portfolio.

The 10 POLIS students will be selected based on the following criteria:

- interest-driving learning in the contents of the Winter School (i.e., relevance to Just Green Transitions) based on the motivation letter;
- academic background and preparation based on the CV and/or the portfolio;
- research skills and attitudes based on the CV and/or the portfolio;

An evaluation committee of the POLIS & Co-PLAN staff involved in the teaching activity will assess the candidates.

Ethics disclaimer: The list of selected candidates will ensure a balanced gender representation. No discrimination is allowed to any ethnicity, race, nationality, sexual, religious, or political orientation. GreenFORCE Team will guarantee the maintenance of a selection process that is fair and equitable and support the informed and responsible decision-making of candidates.

List of Participants

An email will be sent to the selected candidates by the 23rd of January 2025. The list will comprise up to 10 selected students + 2 eligible candidates (reserve list).

The 10 selected students must send their confirmation to fiona_imami@co-plan.org and kejt_dhrami@co-plan.org, communicating their acceptance by the 25th of January 2025. The email should include:

- a specific written communication on any possible disclaimers regarding allergy, communication issues, disabilities and/or special needs, health issues, security issues, and accommodation restrictions (if there are no disclaimers, please indicate as well).

If one of the 10 selected students cancels or does not confirm the above request in their participation in time, the first eligible candidate in the reserve list will be offered their place.

Disclaimer

A minimum of five (10) participants from POLIS is required to activate the programme. The organisational team is NOT accountable if the activity is cancelled for any *force majeure* reason.

General Timeline:

Dates	Before the winter school
20 th of January 2025	Deadline for students' application
23 rd of January 2025	Notification of the results
25 th of January 2025	Deadline for acceptance and finalisation of the list of participants
	Winter school and after
28 th of January 2025	1-day kick-off event (online)
5 th of February 2025	1-day lectures event (online)
12 th of February 2025	1-day lectures event (online)
17 th -21 st of February 2025	Winter School activities in Tirana (5 days)
27 th March	Final presentation (online)

About GreenFORCE Project:

This winter school is part of the HORIZON-WIDERA project "[GreenFORCE. Foster Research Excellence for Green Transition in the Western Balkans](#)" (HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-02-02). The five partner organisations are [Co-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development](#) in Albania as the coordinating partner; [University of Belgrade - Faculty of Geography \(UB-GEF\)](#) in Serbia and the [Center for Economic Analysis Association \(CEA\)](#) in North Macedonia as the two regional partners; and [Nordregio](#), a pan-Nordic research organisation based in Sweden, together with [Politecnico di Torino \(PoliTO\)](#), in Italy, as the leading EU Research Institutions. POLIS University (U_POLIS') in Albania is the affiliate partner of Co-PLAN.

GreenFORCE aims to foster excellence in the Western Balkans' Green Transition scientific research and innovation of Co-PLAN (Albania), CEA (North Macedonia), and UB-GEF (Serbia); to enhance their research profile, strengthening the research and management capacities of their staff, and contributing to convergence between the Western Balkans and the European Union research capacities, as well as to broader policy initiatives for the region. This objective is reached through the twinning partnership of five organisations that work closely to produce territorial knowledge through exploratory research and institutional learning; transfer and exchange knowledge among partner organisations through applying the knowledge management cycle; and engage in networking for sharing, cross-fertilizing and amplifying knowledge at the societal level.

The researchers of the consortium engage in building a joint research project with objectives related to (i) the conceptualisation of Green Transition in the Western Balkans (WB), (ii) the assessment of possible impacts and costs of Just Green Transitions, focusing on components of the pillars of the EU Green Agenda for the WB; (iii) the proposal of a continuous monitoring and assessment framework on Green Transition impacts and costs in the WB, to be used by scientists, researchers and policy-makers in facilitating the Just Green Transitions.

This winter school is the third and final of three stand-alone teaching events that contribute to the co-design, co-evaluation, exchange and sharing of the research practice and results conducted in the project. The events are open to students from U_Polis, UB-GEF and PoliTO. Each event will host up to 20 students, of which 10 will be from the hosting institution; in this case, **U_POLIS will have ten participating students**. Students attending at least one of the stand-alone teaching events may decide to work more thoroughly on this topic through the development of their master thesis under the supervision of one or more professors involved in the winter school.

* For any clarification, please email both fiona_imami@co-plan.org and kejt_dhrami@co-plan.org.

This activity is organised with the support of Co-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development and POLIS University.

Annex 2b – List of Students Selected

Students attending the summer school have agreed on sharing the material

	Name & Surname	University
1	Luka Đurović	UBGeF
2	Nikola Adžemović	UBGeF
3	Mihajlo Đorđević	UBGeF
4	Ana Ristić	UBGeF
5	Lazar Milivojević	UBGeF
6	Stefania Calamita	POLITO
7	Ekinsu Gungordu	POLITO
8	Vedashree Kozhiyalam Sudhakar	POLITO
9	Chiara Difino	POLITO
10	Aida Asadzadeh	POLITO
11	Greta Shehu	POLIS
12	Enkela Poro	Co-PLAN
13	Arsen Toci	POLIS
14	Ergena Luzi	POLIS
15	Ergys Demaj	POLIS
16	Doris Saqe	POLIS
17	Ersi Rryci	POLIS
18	Ledia Sulaj	POLIS
19	Denis Brahja	POLIS
20	Andrea Thomaj	POLIS
21	Alesio Gjoka	POLIS

Annex 3b - The Winter School Agenda

Winter School Kick-OFF

Tuesday 28th of January 2025 | 10:00 – 11:30 (CEST)

Zoom Link:

<https://uso2web.zoom.us/j/86868780150?pwd=Tsl4eNPagsBVDDW4UaFXMNHpgVT9jM.1>

Meeting ID: 868 6878 0150

Passcode: 764036

- | | |
|----------------|--|
| 10.00 – 10.10: | Opening of Winter School and Welcoming of Students
<i>Prof. As. Merita Toska, Vice Rector of POLIS University</i> |
| 10.10 – 10.20 | Presentation of GreenFORCE project – What we've done so far
<i>Dr. Fiona Imami / Dr. Anila Bejko, Project Coordinator (Co-PLAN)</i> |
| 10.20 – 10.30 | GreenFORCE Partner's Presentation
<i>Prof. Giancarlo Cotella (POLITO); Alberto Giacometti (Nordregio);
Dr. Vesna Garvanlieva (CEA); Dr. Aleksandar Djordjevic (UBGeF)</i> |
| 10.30 – 11.00 | Tour de Table – Students' presentation / Icebreaker |
| 11.00 – 11.20 | Introduction to Winter School Topic, Agenda & Main Activities
<i>Dr. Kejt Dhrami, Key Researcher (Co-PLAN)</i> |
| 11.20 – 11.30 | Open Questions & Next Steps |

Online Lectures Event 1

Wednesday 5th of February 2025 | 09.30 – 12.30

Zoom Link:

<https://uso2web.zoom.us/j/86087609986?pwd=alGGBksvpaTdknFFPiLa7pumClxh51.1>

Meeting ID: 860 8760 9986

Passcode: 501872

- | | |
|---------------|---|
| 09.30 – 9.40: | Opening of Lecture Series and Welcoming of Students |
| 09.40 – 10.30 | Lecture 1: What Does It Mean to Be Green? Frameworks for Resilient, Biodiverse, and Healthy Urban Communities
<i>Dr. Kejt Dhrami</i> |
| 10.30 – 10.45 | Short Break |
| 10.45 - 11.45 | Lecture 2: Harnessing Nature: The Promise and Practice of NbS
<i>Hedda Thomson & Alberto Giacometti (Nordregio)</i> |

- 11.45 – 12.20 Lecture 3: Nature-based solutions to healthier cities
Prof. Ass. Anja Ranđelović, University of Belgrade - Faculty of Civil Engineering,
- 12.20 – 12.30 **Questions & Discussion**

Online Lectures Event 2

Wednesday 12th of February 2025 | 09.30 – 12.30

Zoom Link:

<https://us02web.zoom.us/j/83778620891?pwd=A8UyfbLh8JcMuoKue9ne1YNacAB9bv.1>

Meeting ID: 837 7862 0891

Passcode: 400630

- 09.30 – 9.40: Opening of Lecture Series and Welcoming of Students
- 09.40 – 10.30 Lecture 4: Nature-based Solutions for Urban Resilience & Green
Transition: Setting the Scene
Dr. Ombretta Caldarice, POLITO
- 10.30 – 10.45 Short Break
- 10.45 – 11.30 Lecture 5: Cost-Benefit Analysis: Basic Understanding the Economic
Value of Nature-Based Solutions
Vesna Garvanlieva Andonova, CEA
- 11.30 – 12.15 Lecture 6: Urban Heat Islands in Tirana, Albania. Analysis and
Potential Solutions
Dr. Klodian Xhexhi, POLIS University
- 12.15 – 12.30 **Questions & Discussion**

AGENDA

Winter School Activities in Tirana

Monday 17th – Friday 21st 2025

Day 1: Monday 17th 2025

Place: *POLIS University Tirana* | Address: <https://maps.app.goo.gl/KCnTGyu8grv6kDPe6>

Classroom: MAD center

09.00 – 09.30:	Registration & Welcoming Coffee
09.30 – 09.45	Welcoming Speech and Launching of Winter School on-site activities Besnik Aliaj/ Merita Toska & Anila Bejko
09.45 – 10.00	Introduction to Winter School Program Activities Fiona Imami & Kejt Dhrami
10.00 – 11.00	Introductory Lecture: Context of Tirana's Development Doriana Musai
11.00 – 12.00	Case Study Presentation Kejt Dhrami
12.00 – 13.00	Lunch Break @ MoTOWN (4th Floor)
13.00 – 13.30	Group Work Introduction & Group Division
13.30 – 15.00	Getting to Know Your Community - An Experimental Landscape Exercise Silvi Jano & Kejt Dhrami
19.00	Social Gathering @ DUFF Sports Bar Address: https://maps.app.goo.gl/mU848xfbiz1pdLYh9

Day 2: Tuesday 18th 2025

Place: *Study Tour in Tirana Neighborhoods* | TAIWAN Center:

Address: <https://maps.app.goo.gl/ssREeX5Mt7quqVwD6>

09.30 – 12.00:	Study Tour of Tirana A glimpse of the neighborhood transformations in Tirana Dr. Doriana Musai (TBD)
12.00 – 13.00	Joint Lunch @ Zgara Tirana 2 Address: https://maps.app.goo.gl/VW6xMTknteAEbb358
13.00 – 15.00	Group Work on the specific sites (each group divided and supervised) Site 1: Ali Demi Neighbourhood https://maps.app.goo.gl/j2EeB3cANVxSeFix8 Site 2: Twenty-One Neighbourhood https://maps.app.goo.gl/KyEgCEFQRxhVLggY6 Site 3: Technological Park Area https://maps.app.goo.gl/VPgp114cM4mxx4Yd6
15.00	Free arrangements for data gathering/observations at each site

Day 3: Wednesday 19th 2025

Place: *POLIS University Tirana* | Address: <https://maps.app.goo.gl/KCnTGyu8grv6kDPe6>

Classroom: C2 (main building, 3rd floor)

- 09.00 – 09.30: Welcoming Coffee
- 09.30 – 10.30: Evaluating the Resilience of Albanian Indigenous Bulbous Plants on a Green Roof System | Silvi Jano, Agriculture University Tirana
- 10.30 – 11.30: Simulations & Stimulations for JGT | Ledian Bregasi, Polis University
- 11.30 - 12.00: Open Questions & Discussions
- 12.00 – 13.00** **Lunch Break @ MoTOWN (4th Floor)**
- 13.00 – 17.00: Group Work on the cases under the professor's supervision
- 19.00 – 22.00: Social Dinner/Event @ERA Villa
Address: <https://maps.app.goo.gl/DNZcrXjBuVhGvWqDA>

Day 4: Thursday 20th 2025

Place: *Municipality of Tirana | Directorate of Sustainable Development & Natural Emergencies*

Meeting point: *Skanderbeg Square, in front of the National Theater of Opera and Ballet:*

<https://maps.app.goo.gl/L9VZxYVvkQ194Cviz6>

- 10.00 – 12.00: Visit to Municipality of Tirana / Moikom Zeqo Library
Address: <https://maps.app.goo.gl/HN6nMFgh8YPJBB5EA>
- 12.00 – 13.00** **Joint Lunch @ Destil Creative HUB**
Address: <https://maps.app.goo.gl/GdexMMtSgZHLrKfgz>
- 13.00 – 16.00: Group Work at Destil Creative HUB (3rd floor - co-working space)

Day 5: Friday 21th 2025

Place: *POLIS University Tirana* | Address: <https://maps.app.goo.gl/KCnTGyu8grv6kDPe6>

Classroom: C2 (main building, 3rd Floor)

- 09.00 – 10.00: Pitching of Ideas Session
- 10.00 – 11.00: Voting and Co-selection Winning Scenario
- 11.00 - 11.30: Awarding Ceremony (Certificates & Final Photos)
- Cocktail & Final Greetings**
- 15.00: Free time to explore the city

Annex 4b – Teaching Staff

This winter school benefited from the contribution of more than 20 teachers/tutors. The following section provides the list of people involved in with a brief bio each.

Giancarlo Cotella (POLITO UNITE responsible) is associate professor at Politecnico di Torino. His research mainly focuses on European Territorial Governance, in particular on the mutual influence occurring between European Spatial Planning and the spatial governance and planning systems characterising the different Member States. He took active part to several international research projects as ESPON ReSSI, ESPON URRUC, ESPON COMPASS, ESPON SUPER, ESPON METRO, ERASMUS KA2 SPOT and LOTUS and the recently awarded Horizon Europe GreenFORCE and ESPON projects NoStaGeo and TERRES. Since 2023, he serves as Secretary General of the Association of European Schools of Planning.

Erbilin Berisha is assistant professor at Politecnico di Torino. His research focuses on the evolution of Spatial Planning Systems and Territorial Governance in the Western Balkan region in the light of international influence. He is also interested in understanding the geopolitical implications of international initiatives in the region. As research has been involved in numerous international projects like ESPON COMPASS, ESPON SUPER, ESPON SUPER spin-off, ESPON METRO, and more recently is taking an active part in the Horizon Europe GreenFORCE project and in the ESPON projects NoStaGeo and TERRES.

Ombretta Caldarice is Assistant Professor in Urban and Regional Planning at the Interuniversity Department of Regional and Urban Studies and Planning (DIST), Politecnico di Torino. She is a Faculty Affiliate Member of the Responsible Risk Resilience Centre - R3C, Politecnico di Torino. Her research activities focus on the interplay between planning and urban resilience through the lens of planning rules. She has more than ten years of international experience in research, capacity-building, and education on how to make cities more resilient, dealing with the following topics: (i) theories and practices of resilience; (ii) mainstreaming resilience in spatial planning; and (iii) urban codes and techniques for resilience. She is the co-coordinator of the ERASMUS+ Project with the Witwatersrand University Johannesburg on resilience and climate change. She is a member of the scientific committee of the Intensive Training on Urban Resilience (University of Southern of Denmark). She is a member of the Editorial Board of the Springer Book Series "Resilient Cities. Rethinking Urban Transformation."

Kejt Dhrami, Ph.D., is lecturer at Polis University (FPMMU) since 2015. Currently she is coordinator for planning studies in the MSc program, as well as coordinator for spatial planning and GIS in the professional master program. Kejt's academic experiences include subjects such as: planning history; advanced urban development laboratory; final thesis studio; and, previously, planning systems; GIS; urban planning laboratory; urban policies; etc. Alongside her academic engagement, Kejt is also employed as a spatial planning and regional development expert at Co-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development, where she currently manages the Territorial Governance Unit. Her skills extend to GIS database systems management and operationalization. Kejt has managed several initiatives / activities within international projects, funded by USAID, World Bank, IADSA, UNDP, etc., as well as Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe projects.

Aleksandar Djordjevic works as an associate professor at the University of Belgrade – Faculty of Geography. With a background as spatial planner and GIS analyst, his research revolves around the GIS projects implementation, geospatial analyses, and mapping. Dr Djordjevic coordinated numerous GIS projects on local, regional, and national level in Serbia, as well as within international institutions and companies. His current research interests include the "spatialisation" and visualization of just green transition in the European and Western Balkan's contexts.

Klodjan Xhexhi currently serves as Head of the Department of Architecture and Engineering at Polis University, Tirana, Albania. He has accumulated extensive academic experience both nationally and internationally, also contributing significantly to teaching at the Faculty of Architecture and Urbanism (FAU) and Epoka University. After completing his Master of Science in Architecture, he became part of the Hysenbelliu Group, one of Albania's leading conglomerates. Throughout his career, Dr. Xhexhi has demonstrated expertise in both exterior and interior design, as well as planning, by designing and implementing many important architectural projects. An active researcher, Dr. Xhexhi is the author of numerous publications and has participated in various international scientific conferences. He published his first book in architecture immediately after earning his Doctor of Science degree. His scientific interests include building materials, building technology, sustainable architecture, and bioclimatic design. In October 2022, he wrote a second book with the publishing house Springer Nature, an internationally renowned publishing house. To date, Dr. Xhexhi has published over 60 scientific scientific publications and two books, contributing extensively to the academic and professional discussion in architecture.

Vesna Garvanlieva Andonova is an expert on municipal finance, public finance management, and economic analyses. She has significant professional experience and record in project management and consultancy both for the private and the public sector aimed at economic development. Her interest focuses on quantitative and qualitative research and policy analyses in the areas of good governance in public finance management, human capital development, local finance, regional development, etc.

Alberto Giacometti is a Senior Research Advisor at Nordregio. He has a background in human geography, regional development, and spatial planning. Alberto works in projects related to regional innovation systems, resilience, governance, and circular economy. His research interests surround the governance and territorial aspects of industrial path creation, including the ongoing just green transition.

Hedda Thompson has an academic background in environmental science and policy, within both research and communication for sustainable regional development. She has contributed to research on nature-based solutions in urban landscapes, as well as socio-environmental challenges in rural areas. Hedda is especially passionate about ecosystem-based management approaches, green transitions, and building sustainable food systems.

Merita Toska is a Lecturer in Scientific Master Programs at the Faculty of Planning, Environment and Urban Management at POLIS University (Tirana, Albania). Her academic career started at the University of Bologna (Italy), continued in 2007 at the University of Our Lady of Good Counsel (Tirana) and from 2015 at POLIS University as a Lecturer and Researcher. At the same time, Dr Toska is an Expert with over 15 years of professional experience in economic development and public finance issues (engaged in more than 35 national and international projects) at Co-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development.

Yahya Shaker is a PhD Candidate in the Doctoral Programme in Urban and Regional Development (URD) at the Interuniversity Department of Regional & Urban Studies and Planning (DIST) - Politecnico di Torino and University of Turin, a Co-lecturer of the Urban Planning Module in the City and Territory Studio B Course at (DIST) Politecnico di Torino, and a Teaching Assistant in Urban Design, and Urban Planning Courses at the Department of Architecture and Urban Studies (DASU) at Politecnico di Milano. With an international academic background in the fields of Architecture, Engineering, Urban Planning and Policy Design, he has been dedicated to acquire a multitude of professional experiences in the fields of Strategic Territorial Planning, Urban Planning and Design, Urban and Public Policies, and Spatial Governance, alongside collaborating with various world-class universities and research institutes in the European Union and the United States.

Doriana Musaj is an architect and Urban Planner. She completed her Master of Science studies at the Faculty of Civil Engineering, Polytechnic University of Tirana, graduating with an MSc in Urban Planning, in 2008. She also attended the “Landscape and Urban Design” master’s degree, 2011-2013, at Polis University, with a diploma joint with IHS-Institute for Housing and Urban Development Studies, Erasmus. The master’s thesis focuses on the research of the phenomenon of the urbanization of the coastal area with the case study of the bay of Durra, the area of Golem, with an approach examining the institutional and legal overlaps that have generated and stimulated this phenomenon. As the conclusion of the third cycle of studies, she received her doctorate in 2023, with a double degree from the University of Polis, Tirana and that of Ferrara, Italy. The doctoral thesis focuses on the interests and conflicts that are generated by decision-making in the public space of the city, investigating the inherited urban layers and where the theories of urban commons are used as a research lens. Since 2019, it is part of Polis University, collaborating in the subjects of Urban Planning, Urban Regeneration, Cultural Heritage and Technical Urbanism. Starting from September 2022, he is the Deputy Dean of the Faculty of Planning, Environment and Urban Management at POLIS University.

Fiona Imami is a regional development programming, planning & monitoring expert and researcher with a strong educational background in planning and management issues, and a doctoral studies programme in 2021 in the IDAUP (Polis / Ferrara) program. With a professional experience of around 10 years, Fiona has significantly contributed to central and local government institutions in Albania, specializing in strategic document preparation and administrative staff capacity building. Over the years she has worked especially in project implementation and management for local and regional planning and programming, including here drafting of territorial plans, economic development

strategies, regional and national programmers etc. funded by various international institutions such as USAID, ADA, SDC, GIZ and UNDP.

As a researcher Fiona's current interests spans over fostering green transition initiatives, in which she's involved in EU Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe projects funded projects. Additionally, Fiona's academic rigor is sustained by her continuous engagement as lecturer at Polis university and her commitment in authoring and co-authoring a list of scientific and policy papers.

Anila Bejko is the Executive Director of Co-PLAN and has been part of the organization since 2005, contributing her expertise in Territorial Governance. She currently is the coordinator of GreenFORCE Project. With over 20 years of experience, Anila has advised the Albanian government on legal frameworks and strategic documents, particularly in Regional Development reform, Territorial Administrative reform, Decentralization, Fiscal Decentralization strategies, and Territorial Planning reform. Anila holds postgraduate qualifications in Urban Development Policies, Intergovernmental Fiscal Relations & Local Financial Management, a Master's in Housing and Land Development, and an MBA. She brings a wealth of knowledge from her involvement in management, research, and technical expertise in more than 40 donor-funded projects, focusing on green transition, sustainable economic development, urban and spatial planning, city development strategies, regionalization and regional development, and public financial management. She serves academia since 15 years as a researcher and lecturer at Polis University.

Ledio Allkja is a spatial and urban planning expert. He has been working at Co-Plan since 2017 in the Territorial Governance and Planning Department. He conducted his bachelor studies (2011) at the University of West of England in Bristol on Property Development and Planning. Afterwards, continued his master at Radboud University Nijmegen on European Spatial and Environmental Planning (2012), and his PhD on Europeanization of Spatial Planning Systems at the Vienna University of Technology (2020). Since 2012 he has worked also at POLIS University as a lecturer and researcher. His work experience include preparation of general local territorial plans (Zagoria, Krume, Sarande, Shkoder, Mat), preparation of the General National Territorial Plan for Albania, the Integrated Cross Sectorial Plan for the Tirana-Durres area. At Co-PLAN he has been involved in different key projects in the areas of Urban Development and Management (PLGP), Disaster Risk Reduction and adaptive planning, housing etc. He has over 8 years of work experience in research, project writing, project implementation and project management.

Elona Karafili is a qualified professional in the field of economic development. She is a lecturer and researcher at POLIS University, Tirana, Albania since 2007. She holds a PhD in Urban Planning from Ferrara University and Polis University. Elona currently holds the position of the Deputy Rector of POLIS University. Her main topics of interest and expertise include regional economic development and territorial competitiveness, which she has explored through a number of projects that focus on place-based innovation. Dr. Karafili has extensive experience in designing and directing research and capacity building projects. She is enthusiastic to strengthen the innovation ecosystem in Albania through fostering co-creative processes, academia-business collaboration and knowledge transfer, startup support and commercialization of research.

Ledian Bregasi is Dean of the Faculty of Architecture and Design at POLIS University where he teaches advanced architectural design since 2010. Ledian Bregasi was granted the Ph.D. title in Architecture, Theory and Design for his thesis focusing on the emergent properties of complex systems and their possible applications in architectural and urban design from “Sapienza” University of Rome from where he had previously graduated in the Architecture UE integrated master program. In 2013 and 2021 he is co-curator of the first and fourth editions of the Tirana Design Week, a biennial event organized by POLIS University. Since 2012 he is director of The Albanian Union of Architects and Urban Planners, an association of professionals that has among its objectives the advancement of the architectural debate and the promotion of professional excellence.

Silvi Jano is an urban & Environmental planner with over 10 years of experience in landscape planning and design at local, regional, and national levels. With academic experience at the University of Van Hall Larenstein, Holland and TU WienN, Vienna, Austria, and recently as part of his PhD. studies at Geisenheim University in Germany. Currently full-time lecturer at the Agricultural University of Tirana, Dep. of Horticulture and Landscape Architecture. Expert in the field of landscape & environmental planning and coordinator of community-based projects, specifically public places making. Fields of interest comprise environmental planning, ecological design, and sky gardening with native vegetation within the Mediterranean context.

Annex 5b – ToRs for Students Work

International Winter School

Scaling down Green Transition

Co-creating Nature-Based Solutions at the neighborhood level

TERMS OF REFERENCE

Description

The students will be developing **2 scenarios** for climate neutrality for each of the 3 target areas. The scenarios will include design and implementation of nature-based solutions, prioritizing the use of the open / public or semi-public space. The students will be requested to analyze the current environmental and livability conditions, to assess current and future ecosystem services from the urban greenery and other NBS, and to take into account the community engagement and willingness to pay/ co-finance.

The produced results will capitalize on current knowledge generated through the research on '**Net-Zero transition for Post-Communist Urban Neighbourhoods in Tirana**'. **An abstract can be found below:**

The research titled "Net-Zero Transition for Post-Communist Urban Neighborhoods in Tirana" explores the efforts towards achieving net-zero emission buildings in large panel apartment blocks constructed between the 1960s and 1980s. These buildings, typical of Albania's post-communist urban development, are characterized by poor energy efficiency and outdated construction techniques. As Albania aligns itself with the European Green Deal and seeks to meet the pillars of the Western Balkans Green Transition Agenda, this research offers a comprehensive analysis of the socio-economic and environmental implications of transitioning towards net-zero energy buildings (NZEB) in these areas.

The research develops four transition scenarios to examine possible pathways toward energy efficiency and climate neutrality in these neighborhoods. Scenario 0 is a baseline scenario where no action is taken to improve energy performance or reduce carbon emissions. In this case, the buildings remain inefficient, leading to ongoing high energy consumption and exacerbating issues such as energy poverty, particularly as energy prices increase and buildings continue to deteriorate.

In contrast, Scenario 1 focuses on enhancing the energy performance of these buildings by improving insulation, upgrading windows, and installing more efficient heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) systems. This scenario is designed to bring buildings closer to Class A energy performance, which would significantly reduce energy demand, improve comfort for residents, and lower annual energy costs. Scenario 2 builds upon Scenario 1 by introducing renewable energy solutions, such as photovoltaic (PV) panels and rainwater harvesting systems. These additions not only improve the buildings' energy performance but also contribute to climate neutrality by offsetting energy consumption with renewable energy production. Scenario 3 presents a more radical approach, proposing the complete redevelopment of the neighborhoods, replacing the existing structures with modern, energy-efficient buildings. This scenario requires substantial investment and policy support but offers the potential for the most significant environmental and socio-economic benefits in the long term.

The research employed a mixed-methods approach, combining both qualitative and quantitative analyses. Data were gathered through surveys, interviews, observations, and energy audits conducted in three neighborhoods in Tirana: Ali Demi, 21 Dhjetori, and Ish-Teknologjiku. These areas are representative of the broader socio-economic profile of Tirana, with a mix of elderly residents, consolidated families, and younger renters.

In terms of household survey results, the data revealed that the majority of residents have lived in these neighborhoods for many years, with an average apartment size of 71.5 square meters. A significant portion of the respondents rely heavily on electricity for their energy needs, particularly for heating, cooling, and cooking. However, energy efficiency is low, with old appliances and inadequate insulation leading to high energy consumption, especially during the winter months. Many residents have a basic awareness of energy-saving solutions, but the willingness to invest in or co-finance such measures is limited, mainly due to financial constraints. Although there is broad recognition of the Green Transition's importance, only a minority of respondents have actively adopted energy-efficient appliances or technologies, and most are only willing to support such interventions if substantial financial aid or co-financing is available.

The environmental performance of these neighborhoods was also assessed through air quality monitoring and microclimate modeling. The research found that the urban layout and construction materials in these neighborhoods contribute to poor environmental performance, particularly in terms of air pollution and urban heat retention. The presence of green spaces and urban greenery, while limited, plays a crucial role in mitigating some of these issues by reducing air pollution and regulating temperatures. However, the overall lack of green infrastructure in these areas enhances the urban heat island effect and contributes to even poorer air quality.

The energy audit conducted as part of the research revealed that the current energy performance of the buildings is suboptimal. Most of the buildings are rated between energy classes D and E, with high energy consumption due to poor insulation, inefficient windows, and outdated HVAC systems. The research proposed several technical solutions to improve energy performance, such as adding wall and roof insulation, replacing windows and doors with energy-efficient alternatives, and upgrading heating systems. These measures could reduce energy consumption by up to 50%, depending on the building and apartment typology. For example, a typical 1+1 apartment could see its energy consumption drop from 140 kWh/m² per year to 79.5 kWh/m², leading to significant annual savings in both energy and financial terms.

In Scenario 2, the installation of photovoltaic panels on rooftops was modeled using specialized software, showing promising results. The proposed PV system would cover 78% of the available rooftop space and could generate up to 408,415 kWh per year, significantly reducing the buildings' reliance on the national grid. The installation of rainwater harvesting systems was also explored, with potential benefits including the reduction of water demand from the public supply, contributing to more sustainable urban water management and mitigating the urban heat island effect.

A cost-benefit analysis (CBA) was conducted to assess the economic feasibility of the proposed scenarios, considering both the costs and benefits over a 16-year reference period. The analysis quantified energy savings, reductions in carbon emissions, and improvements in public health due to better air quality and lower energy costs. In the energy efficiency scenario (Scenario 1), the investment required to improve the energy performance of the buildings was estimated at around 900,000 Euros, but the annual energy savings would amount to 475,761 kWh, translating into significant financial savings for residents. The internal rate of return (IRR) for these investments was calculated to be over 17%, with a payback period of just under six years, making this a financially viable intervention.

In Scenario 2, the combination of energy efficiency measures and renewable energy production through PV systems increased the overall benefits. The PV system alone was projected to save 408,415 kWh of electricity annually, with substantial reductions in CO₂ emissions, making a strong case for integrating renewable energy solutions in these neighborhoods. The economic analysis showed that the system would generate revenues of approximately 1 million Euros over its 25-year lifespan, with a payback period of around six years. These results

demonstrate that a combination of energy efficiency and renewable energy solutions can provide both environmental and financial returns.

However, the redevelopment scenario (Scenario 3), while offering the greatest potential for long-term sustainability, presents significant challenges in terms of upfront investment and the complexity of implementation. Redeveloping entire neighborhoods from scratch would require substantial financial resources and policy changes, particularly in terms of land use and property rights. Although this scenario promises the highest environmental and social returns, it is also the most complex to implement due to the need for coordination of multiple stakeholders within the detailed local planning process.

In conclusion, the research highlights the importance of transitioning Tirana's post-communist urban neighborhoods towards net-zero energy buildings by 2040, favoring a scenario which combines energy efficiency with renewable energy production, thus providing great benefits in terms of sustainability and cost savings.

Based on the research findings and the preliminary data analyzed, the students will be requested to design a model of NBS to fit into the Scenario 2 implementation. The definition of NBS according to [IUCN](#) will be used for this purpose. Moreover, the students will be supported through the methods designed by the [Net Zero Cities platform](#), following these resources:

- GHG emissions / Scope 1, 2 & 3 <https://netzerocities.app/resource-3238>
- Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR) / Negative emissions <https://netzerocities.app/resource-3248>
- Urban heat island (UHI) effect mitigation - Nearly Zero Energy Buildings (NZEBS) <https://netzerocities.app/resource-3364>
- Near Zero/ Positive Energy Districts (PEDs) <https://netzerocities.app/resource-3354>
- Positive Energy Buildings (PEBs) <https://netzerocities.app/resource-3374>
- Eco-districts / Green neighbourhoods <https://netzerocities.app/resource-3258>
- Urban heat island effect mitigation - Evaporate Cooling <https://netzerocities.app/resource-3384>
- Smart Grid <https://netzerocities.app/resource-3268>
- Urban green space ecology <https://netzerocities.app/resource-3308>
- Carbon capture and storage (CCS) and utilization (CCU) <https://netzerocities.app/resource-3318>

Ultimately, the students will have to assess the tangible benefits of their NBS in the following form:

1. Accounting for ecosystem services provided by the intervention (in quantifiable form)
2. Evaluating the impact of the interventions in 3 dimensions: Health; Economic Growth; Inclusivity (in quantifiable – wherever necessary – and nonmonetary way)
3. A summary of the overall NBS, discussed in 5 dimensions (Richter scale) as shown below

Case studies

Area 1 – [‘21 dhjetori’ neighborhood](#)

Area Surface	Area Perimeter	No. of buildings
11,941 m ²	521 m	11

Area 2- Ex-Technological park

Area Surface	Area Perimeter	No. of buildings
10,703 m ²	812 m	7

Area 3- [Ali Demi](#)

Area Surface	Area Perimeter	No. of buildings
13,687 m2	815 m	9

Day 1

Getting to know the case studies

The students will be expected to learn more about the case studies and the research conducted, while designing the list of parameters that they would like to measure.

By the end of the day they will need to fill the 2 tables below, focusing on the measurements and assessments of Ecosystem Services Supply; and Environmental Indicators.

Assessing the demand of the area – aka Environmental / Societal targets

Health	Why we need it? How much improvement?	Economic Growth	Why we need it? How much improvement?	Inclusivity	Why we need it? How much improvement?
Improved air quality					
<i>Add as needed</i>					

Assessing ecosystem services supply

Urban ecosystem service	Supply indicator	Method and calculation	Value per unit	Is it relevant for the area? 1-not relevant – 5 very relevant
Microclimate regulation (cooling)	Cooling capacity of green infrastructure	<i>Add here based on literature review</i>		
Habitat provision	Relative richness of focal species			
Recreation	Recreation Opportunity Spectrum			
Noise mitigation	Reduction of traffic noise at selected receivers (residential buildings)			
Air purification	PM10 deposition			
	CO2 sequestration			
Runoff mitigation	Runoff avoided due to infiltration			
Other? Add as needed				

In the end we will have a clear picture if the 'demand' and 'supply' match during our design process.

Moreover, during day 1 the students will have to be acquainted with the results of the **Household surveys**, so that they can understand the community behaviour in greater detail.

Day 2

Data gathering, field visit

The students will be able to visit the sites in a 2-hour dedicated time slot. They will engage in different activities, summarized as follows:

Visual and photographic mapping of built environment / 3rd landscape / urban pockets / building facades

1. Mapping of existing vegetation
2. Community observation and interviews: getting to know more in detail who lives there and how they

A field trip reference format can be found in annex. Students will be able to work independently after the site visit to further conceptualize their intervention plans, taking into account the demand / target environmental performance.

Day 3

First design mock up. Simulations / trial and error

The students will work in parallel with the design of NBS for the 2 scenarios, and the estimation of ecosystem services achieved by the design. Through dedicated assistance, they will be able to design a neighbourhood-level simulation using Rhino, to assess the best location for the proposed intervention.

Moreover, they will be assisted to design environmental performance simulation through EnviMET and QGIS. If necessary, the students will employ a space syntax analysis to analyse the accessibility of the built environment.

Lastly, all teams will design a matrix of trees / vegetation types to include in their design.

Day 4 Getting hands dirty

Work in groups to finalize the design, the assessments and final presentation. Horizontal tutors will provide guidance throughout the whole day.

Day 5 Community simulation game

The students will have to pitch their final idea in form of a 15-minute presentation. The 2 final scenarios for each team will be printed out. The participants (aka. other team members and tutors) will be assigned a specific role as community representative, with a unique background. They will then vote on their preferred idea based on the role they are simulating. The winning idea for each team will not necessarily reflect the most desired outcome by the designer. It will be up to the students to convince the community why to choose an outcome that is best for the community at large (aka ranking best at the star-tool Richter scale)

Content of the work:

We expect each team to work in creative way to showcase their NBS scenarios in most effective form. In general the structure of outputs can be the following:

- An overview of observations in the area
- Mapping of behaviours, feelings, environmental concerns (through sketches or collages)
- Summary of key demands for the area based on individual assessment and case research
- Introduction to the vision for NBS – conceptualization of 2 scenarios
- Area-level analysis and simulation using Rhino; Space Syntax, EnviMET, etc.
- Design of scenarios (scale 1:500)
- Presentation of vegetation matrix
- Assessment of ecosystem services provided by each scenario (quantified)
- Compilation of the Star Tool based on 5 indicators for each scenario, with motivation for the choice.

Final deliverable:

On Friday:

- A powerpoint presentation summarizing the process and results achieved (to be presented in 15 minutes)
- 2 posters in A2 format, showcasing each of the designed scenarios (Annex attached)
- Any supporting / additional visual tool you need to support your work

End of Winter School (*March, exact date tbd*)

- A report summarizing the analysis, results, and the outcome of the voting (10 pages max – Structure in Annex)
- Revised Scenario design (if needed)
- Powerpoint presentation – final event (online)

